

**The Effects of Sleep and Stress on Resistance to Distractor Interference
among Shift and Non-shift Workers**

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7PS999: Masters Research Project

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2021

Word count 7968 words

Declarations:

'I declare that this assessment is my own work and that I have correctly acknowledged the work of others using APA referencing style. This assessment is in accordance with University guidance on good academic conduct.'

'I declare that confidentiality of people discussed in this work is maintained; there is no identifiable information of these individuals.'

Abstract

Shiftwork has serious effects on mental and physical health and on cognition. The current study investigated the effects of shiftwork, sleep, and stress on Resistance to distractor interference (RDI). This study is between-subject non-parametric design using Mann-Whitney U test. A total of 208 participants were recruited online. The flanker task was administered to test RDI. The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) was used to assess sleep quality and the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) was used to assess stress. Shift workers scored significantly higher on PSQI than non-shift workers. Interference effect of good sleepers was closer to average than poor sleepers. There was non-significant effects of neither shiftwork nor stress on interference effect. Evening chronotypes had significantly higher scores on PSQI and PSS compared to morning chronotypes. Higher scores on PSS were significantly correlated with higher scores on PSQI. The current study demonstrate that shiftwork negatively impacts sleep quality, and poor sleep quality is linked to increased distractibility, jeopardizing individuals' health and the safety of work environment. However, shiftwork and stress do not directly influence distractibility. Additionally, evening chronotypes have poor sleep and higher stress, and increased stress may lead to poor sleep quality and vice versa. These results must be taken with caution as the study did not control for length of service of shift workers. These findings have implications for employers of shift workers by devising solutions to their schedules that minimize the consequence of shiftwork on sleep quality.

Keywords: Resistance to distractor interference, shiftwork, stress, sleep, chronotypes

Introduction

Executive functions

Executive functions (EF) are higher-order cognitive processes involved in reasoning, planning, formulating goals, organizing and can control lower-level automatic responses (Cummings & Miller, 2007; Norman & Shallice, 1980; Schneider & Shiffrin, 1977). EFs are important for spur-of-the-moment responding and decision-making (Moran & Garndner, 2018), especially in novel situations, where prior knowledge and skills may be helpful but insufficient to deal with the current task (Posner & DiGirolamo, 1998).

Deficits in EFs are prevalent in people with psychological disorders and brain damage (Cummings & Miller, 2007), in children with specific language impairment (Pauls & Archibald, 2016), and in people with neuropsychological disorders such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (Nigg, 2001), obsessive compulsive disorder, and autism spectrum disorder (Andersen et al., 2015; Geurts et al., 2014). Issues in EFs are not confined to psychological disorders. Many factors influence the efficiency of EFs, such as: genetics (Friedman et al., 2008), sleep deprivation (Anderson & Platten, 2011), drug and alcohol use (Le Berre et al., 2017; Nigg et al., 2006), stress (Shields et al., 2016), and parent's educational level (Ardila et al., 2005). Breakdown in any of EFs could hinder the affected person's social and professional life (Lezak, 1982).

Researchers classified EFs into a number of subcomponents. Delis et al. (2001) identified nine components: Flexibility of thinking, inhibition, problem-solving, planning, impulse control,

concept formation, abstract thinking, and creativity. Fisk and Sharp (2004) identified four subcomponents: shifting, updating, inhibition, and verbal fluency. Miyake et al. (2000) identified three subcomponents: inhibition, shifting, and updating.

Early models portrayed EFs as a unitary function (e.g. Baddeley, 1983; Norman & Shallice, 1980), however, recent research challenged this idea pointing to a non-unitary nature (Glisky et al., 2021; Miyake et al., 2000). Similarly, researchers have differing opinions about the unity and diversity of a component of EFs, namely, inhibition control.

Inhibition control

Researchers put many definitions forward to explain inhibition control. Nigg (2000) defined inhibition as the suppression of internal or external stimulus that interferes or slows down a primary response. Gorfain and MacLeod (2007) defined cognitive inhibition as the controlled or automatic act of stopping or overriding of a mental process partially or completely. Thus, inhibition can refer to ability to suppress or resist inappropriate internal or external tempting distractions and urges that can get in the way of achieving one's goals, these distractions may be thoughts, behaviors, emotions, or attention (Aron, 2007; Diamond, 2013).

Researchers identified a different number of components. Harnishfeger (1995) identified three types of inhibition. First type is behavioral inhibition, which refers to the suppression of motor behaviors, such as resisting temptations. Second type is cognitive inhibition, which is the suppression of previous memory contents. Third type is resistance to interference, which is the suppression of potentially attention-capturing processes or contents. Nigg (2000) classified eight types of inhibition, they are grouped under three main classes; executive or effortful inhibition, motivational inhibition, and automatic inhibition. Nigg (2000) classified effortful inhibition into different types, which are very similar to Harnishfeger's (1995) classification: interference

control, cognitive inhibition, and behavioral inhibition. However, Nigg (2000) identified a new type and that is oculomotor, which refers to the effortful suppression of reflexive eye movement. Lustig et al. (2007) defined three functions for inhibition. First function was access, which occurs at the beginning of the information processing stage to prevent irrelevant information from gaining access. Second function was deletion, which deletes irrelevant information that have gained access to the information process but later was recognized as irrelevant. Third function was restraint, which suppresses irrelevant information for the current situation.

Although researchers identified different functions of inhibition, some of these components are the same but are referred to by different terms. Prepotent response inhibition, which is the active suppression of behavioral automatic responses (Bisset et al., 2009; Friedman & Miyake, 2004), is referred to as response inhibition (Tiego et al., 2018), behavioral inhibition (Diamond, 2013; Nigg, 2000; Stahl et al., 2014), and attention restraint (Kane et al., 2016). RDI, the term used in the current study, refers to the resistance of thoughts or perceptual distractions that are irrelevant to the current task (Bisset et al., 2009; Diamond, 2013; Friedman & Miyake, 2004), is also referred to as attentional inhibition (Tiego et al., 2018), interference control (Nigg, 2000), selective attention (Diamond, 2013), stimulus interference (Stahl et al., 2014), interference suppression (Brydges et al., 2012), and attention constraint (Kane et al., 2016). Resistance to proactive interference, which is the suppression of previous memory intrusions that are no longer relevant to the current pursued goal or action (Bisset et al., 2009; Friedman & Miyake, 2004), is referred as cognitive inhibition (Nigg, 2000). It was previously noted that the term interference and inhibition were used interchangeably (Gorfein & MacLeod, 2007). This may be due to the non-unified terminology, which is problematic as it can lead to confusion.

The confusion in inhibition is not only in the terminology, it is prevalent in the relationship between its components. There is strong evidence that both response inhibition and RDI have low correlations with resistance to proactive interference (Bisset et al., 2009; Friedman & Miyake, 2004; Stahl et al., 2014), indicating that resistance to proactive interference is an independent function. However, the relationship between response inhibition and RDI is debatable. Some research points to a high correlation and a strong relationship between response inhibition and RDI (Friedman & Miyake, 2004; Verbruggen et al., 2004; Verbruggen et al., 2006). While other research indicates a separability (Bisset et al., 2009; Brydges et al., 2012; Brydges et al., 2013; Stahl et al., 2014; Tiego et al., 2018), and low correlations (Rey-Mermet et al., 2018).

The differences between RDI and response inhibition is seen in many ways. First, response inhibition refers to the active suppression at the behavioral level while RDI refers to active suppression at the thought-level (Friedman & Miyake, 2004) Second, it was noted that RDI and response inhibition happen at different stages ((Brydges et al., 2012; Diamond, 2013; Friedman & Miyake, 2004), and that successful RDI takes longer time than successful response inhibition (Brydges et al., 2012). Third, certain deficits are linked to one component and not the other. Korke et al. (2021) found that delays in word production to be attributed to interference control and not by later stages, such as response inhibition. Fourth, using ERP techniques, it was found that RDI and response inhibition originate from different neural regions (Brydges et al., 2012), and have distinct neural mechanisms (Xie et al., 2017). These differences between RDI and response inhibition may indicate different cognitive requirements and, therefore, challenge their unity.

The confusion around inhibition is conspicuous, which led many researchers to suggest different approaches when dealing with inhibition, including avoiding it. Gorfein and MacLeod (2007) suggested considering other behavioral phenomena, ones that have solid theoretical load, when studying inhibition, such as deploying attention to select relevant information instead of inhibiting irrelevant information. Aron (2007) argues that inhibition could be useful in some domains, however, it has been overused and that many behavioral results could be explained without it, and suggested to steer our attention to other components such as the working memory. However, EFs rely on each other and can overlap (Cummings & Miller, 2007), a deficit in one executive function may be a result of a deficit in another function. In order to apply interventions to address that specific function, such as sleep extension (Wilckens et al., 2014) or targeted training (Klingberg et al., 2005), it is important to study these functions individually. This includes the study of inhibition-related functions.

Inhibition-related functions are affected by many factors including stress levels (Shields et al., 2019), and sleep deprivation (Chuah et al., 2006; Drummond et al., 2006), which are prevalent among shift workers (Elhami Athar et al., 2020). Compromised RDI can lead to increased distractibility (Anderson & Horne, 2006; Lee et al., 2015), which can have serious impact on the safety of the work environment.

Shiftwork

Shiftwork refers to work schedules that fall outside the typical window of 8 am to 5 pm (McMenamin, 2007). According to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics 16% of the workforce had non-daytime shift schedules in 2017-2018, this included night-shifts, evening-shifts, rotating-shifts, split-shifts, and other irregular shifts (U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2019).

Shiftwork is associated with many ailments and serious diseases, such as: obesity (Karlsson et al., 2001), higher stress levels and higher cortisol (Morales et al., 2019). Shift workers are at higher risk of having mental health issues. Previous reports showed shift workers had more depressed mood and anxiety (Morales et al., 2019; Torquati et al., 2019), were more susceptible to negative mood effects (Challepa et al., 2020), and at higher risk of dementia (Nabe-Nielsen et al., 2019). The associated cognitive decline was detected in various jobs, including: airline crew (Cho et al., 2000; O'Hagen et al., 2019), and on-call medical residents (Morales et al., 2019). The cognitive consequences of shiftwork can take years to fully subside (Marquie, 2014; Titova et al., 2016).

The majority of research agrees that shiftwork is associated with less efficient EFs, these impairments have been evident in many areas of EFs, including: psychomotor vigilance (Adams & Venter, 2021; Anderson et al., 2012; Kwak et al., 2020; McHill & Wright, 2019), sustained attention (Chellappa et al., 2019; Cheng, 2017; Santhi, 2007), visual-motor performance (Chellappa et al., 2019), cognitive flexibility (Cheng et al., 2017), short term memory (Deary & Tait, 1987), visuospatial working (Elhami Athar et al., 2020), working memory (Zhao et al., 2021), and inhibition (Esmaily et al., 2021).

Shiftwork is associated with higher risk of making errors, such as discrepancies in patient reports (Ruutiainen et al., 2013), decreased threat detection during luggage security screening (Basner et al., 2008), higher risk of motor accidents (Schlick et al., 2020), and increased distractibility (Anderson & Horne, 2006; Lee et al., 2015), which has been attributed to compromised EFs (Chellappa et al., 2019; Cheng, 2017) and RDI (Esmaily et al. 2021). Many studies investigated the effects of shiftwork on EFs (e.g., Adams & Venter, 2021; Chellappa et al., 2019), however, only a few looked into the effects of shiftwork on RDI.

Shiftwork and inhibition

Esmaily et al. (2021) investigated inhibition among shiftwork nurses. Using the Stroop task they tested shift workers before and after their shifts. Esmaily et al. (2021) found interference effect to increase after shifts measured using proportion correct (PC) but not reaction time (RT). Among similar population, Kaliyaperumal et al. (2017) investigated inhibition, using the Stroop task. They reported a decline in inhibition performance after night shifts. The measurement of inhibition performance was not clearly mentioned and was described as test scores, so it is not clear whether this refers to accuracy, RT, or both. However, Kaliyaperumal et al. (2017) tested participants after three days of consecutive night shift, which is enough time to allow for adaptation (Chang et al., 2011), reflecting more accurate effects of shiftwork. Studies by Esmaily et al. (2021) and Kaliyaperumal et al. (2017) were within-subject design using the Stroop task. While this study design eliminates individual differences (von Bastian et al., 2020), it can lower reliability as the subjects get used to the task (Rabbitt, 1997). Especially, when using the Stroop task, where participants performance has shown to improve after repeating the task (Wostmann et al., 2013). Though, in Kaliyaperumal et al. (2017) study there was a month gap between day and night shift testing, which may have lessened practice effects.

Elhami Athar et al. (2020) tested inhibition among shift and non-shift workers using Continuous Performance Task. Day workers had higher accuracy than shift-workers, however, RT differences were not significant. The tasks in this study were not administered immediately after the work shift, in contrast with other studies (i.e. Bartel et al., 2004; Esmaily et al., 2021), thus, minimizing immediate effects of sleep deprivation and perhaps reflecting more accurate shiftwork effects.

Bartel et al. (2004) tested inhibition among resident anesthetists before and after night duty. Using a battery test, participants had to select the right target while ignoring other stimuli. It was found that RT was significantly increased after night duty, however, PC was not affected. In Bartel et al. (2004) study, the performance of RTs and accuracy rates were compared separately. Analyzing RTs or PCs separately may lead to contradictory conclusions (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019), this is because of speed-accuracy tradeoff (SAT), where RTs and PCs point to different directions, making it difficult to draw accurate conclusions.

McHill and Wright (2019) studied inhibition in a simulated-night shift approach. Using the Stroop task, McHill and Wright (2019) found the number of PCs and median RTs to decrease after simulated night shift. However, interference effect measured by RTs was not affected. The participants practiced the Stroop task beforehand, which may lower the reliability of the task (Wostmann et al., 2013). In McHill and Wright (2019) study, the measurement of interference effect relied on RTs alone, this can be problematic, especially in the presence of SATs, where participants compromise accuracy in order to respond fast or vice versa. To reduce the effects of SATs, researchers can give instructions to participants to respond as fast as possible while maintaining accuracy, as is the case in McHill and Wright (2019) study. However, this method might not be ideal because participants may not follow instructions throughout all trials of the task, especially that performance can vary within the same subject and among different conditions (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019). Another way to deal with SATs is to eliminate participants with higher error rates than 15% (Bruyer & Brysbaert, 2011). However, this may not be suitable in a study with higher error rates.

Relying on RTs or PCs alone, including when measuring interference effect, can be problematic, because they are sensitive to SATs and may lead to unreliable results (Draheim et

al., 2019), also, analyzing either one alone may lead to contradictory results (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019), especially in the presence of SATs. To tackle this issue, it has been strongly suggested to combine RTs and PCs into a single measurement (Bruyer & Brysbaert, 2011; Draheim et al., 2016; Draheim, 2019; Hughes et al., 2014; Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019; Muller et al., 2020; Vanderdonck, 2021). Many methods have been devised including: Inverse Efficiency Score (IES) (Townsend and Ashby, 1983), Binning Procedure (Draheim et al., 2016), Rate Correct Score by Woltz and Was (2006) (Vandierendonck, 2021), Linear Integrated Speed-Accuracy Score (LISAS) (Vandierendonck, 2017), and Balanced Integrated Score by (BIS) (Liesefeld et al., 2015). The use of some of these methods is strictly limited to certain situations. For example, the IES is used when proportion of error (PE) is less than 10% and there is no sign of SATs (Bruyer & Brysbaert, 2011). The same applies to LISAS (Vandierendonck, 2021). When these rules are not met, the BIS serves as a great tool, as it cancels the effects of SATs compared to other methods (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019), by giving equal weights to both RTs and PEs (Liesefeld et al., 2017).

Most studies investigating the effects of shiftwork on RDI used the Stroop task (i.e. Esmaily et al., 2021; Kaliyaperumal et al., 2017; McHill & Wright, 2019), which taps response inhibition more than RDI (Friedman & Miyake, 2004), compared to the flanker task that has shown to be sensitive at measuring RDI (Bisset et al., 2009; Forstmann et al., 2008; Friedman & Miyake, 2004), and is less susceptible to task impurity (Forstman et al., 2008). The difference between these tasks is evident from correlation studies. Bender (2017) found that the flanker task has zero correlation with Stop-Signal Task, Go-Nogo Task, Single Response Selection Task, Stroop Task, and Attentional Blink. Also, Rouder and Haaf, (2019) found no significant

correlation between the flanker task and the Stroop task, indicating that they might be recruiting different cognitive functions.

Also, there has been inconsistencies in the literature regarding the measurement of interference effect, where most studies relied on RTs alone, measured RTs and PEs separately (Bartel et al., 2004; Elhami Athar et al. 2020), or the measurement was not mentioned clearly (Kaliyaperumal et al., 2017).

Therefore, the current study is set to investigate the effects of sleep and stress on RDI using the flanker task by combining both RTs and PCs into one variable using BIS, which is especially suitable for a between-subject design (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019). The study will also look into the effects of chronotypes on shiftwork, stress, and sleep. This is because shiftwork and sleep quality seem to be modulated by chronotypes (Juda et al., 2013). Additionally, the relationship between stress and sleep were explored. It is hypothesized that shift workers will have less efficient RDI than non-shift workers, poor sleepers will have less RDI than good sleepers, and high stress group will have less efficient RDI than low stress group.

Methods

Design

This study was between-subject non-parametric using a Mann-Whitney U test investigating the effects of sleep and stress on RDI among shift and non-shift workers. Three categorical variables were work shifts, sleep quality, and stress levels. Dependent variable (DV) was interference effect and was measured on a continuous scale. Additionally, a Mann-Whitney U was used to test the effects chronotype on sleep and stress. Also, a Spearman's rank-order correlation was run to determine the relationship between sleep and stress.

Dependent variable was interference effect measured using BIS and RTs. Interference effect is the difference scores of incompatible and compatible trials (Eriksen & Eriksen, 1974), or incompatible and neutral trials (Friedman & Miyake, 2004; Gartner & Strobel, 2021). In this study both compatible and neutral trials were used as a baseline (Rey-Mermet et al., 2018). Therefore, four DVs were calculated: $BIS_{\text{incompatible-compatible}}$, $BIS_{\text{incompatible-neutral}}$, $RT_{\text{incompatible-compatible}}$, and $RT_{\text{incompatible-neutral}}$.

Primary DVs combined both RTs and PEs using the BIS. This was done by calculating z-scores for RT and PC ($PC = 1 - PE$) to bring them to the same scale, then subtract one standardized score from the other (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019). Following the equation: $BIS_{ij} = Z_{PCij} - Z_{RTij}$, where $Z_{PCij} = (PC_{ij} - \overline{PC}) / S_{PC}$, and $Z_{RTij} = (RT_{ij} - \overline{RT}) / S_{RT}$ (see Vandierendonck, 2021). On the BIS a score of 0 is considered average (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019), therefore, scores closer to 0 are closer to average, indicating more efficient interference effect. The BIS is used as a primary DV and not RT, because BIS cancels the effects of SATs (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019), compared to RT that is more sensitive to SATs and less reliable (Draheim et al., 2019).

Interference effect was also measured using the difference scores of RTs alone, this is only to allow for study comparisons, because RT difference scores are the most commonly reported measurement of interference effect. Smaller interference effect reflects more efficient ability to overcome distractions (von Bastian et al., 2020).

First categorical variable was work shifts. First group was shiftwork (night shift, rotating shift, etc.). Second group was non-shift, this included participants that are always on a day shift.

Second categorical variable was sleep quality. Participants were divided into two groups based on their scores on the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) (Buysse et al., 1989). Scores

on this scale range from 0 (no difficulty sleeping) to 21 (severe difficulty sleeping). A cut-off point of 5 was used (Buysse et al., 1989). Scores below or equal to 5 were "good sleepers" and scores above 5 were "poor sleepers".

Third categorical variable was stress, participants were divided into two groups depending on their scores on the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) (Cohen et al., 1983). Scores on this scale range from 0 to 56, higher scores indicating higher perceived stress. There are no suggested cut-offs for this scale as it is not considered a diagnostic tool (Cohen & Williamson, 1988), therefore, a median split of 26 was used. Accordingly, scores below or equal to 26 were "low stress" and scores higher than 26 were "high stress".

Participants

G*Power calculations (Faul et. al., 2009) suggested a sample size of 210 participants (effect size 0.25, power 0.95). The sample comprised of 208 participants (127 males, mean age \pm standard deviation (SD) was 28.45 ± 8.09 years), of which 80 were non-shift workers, 109 shift workers, and 19 unemployed. The unemployed were added to the non-shift worker group as they would have similar sleep/wake pattern to the non-shift workers. Participants were recruited online via Prolific.com, The University of Derby Online's (UDOL) Master's Research Project's discussion boards, Survey Circle. Individuals with sleeping disorders and individuals with psychological disorders were excluded from the study. This is because inhibition control seems to be negatively affected by sleeping disorders, such as, insomnia (Covassin et al., 2011), and psychological disorders, such as: autism spectrum disorders (Geurts et al., 2014), attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and obsessive compulsive disorder (van Velzen et al., 2014).

Materials:

The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (Buysse et al., 1989) (see Appendix E) was used to assess sleep habits during the past month and was hosted on Qualtrics. It consists of 19 self-rated questions, for example, ‘during the past month, how often have you had trouble had trouble sleeping because you had bad dreams?’, answers would be: ‘not during the past month’, ‘less than once a week’, ‘once or twice a week’, or ‘more than three times a week’.

The Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1983) (see Appendix E) was used to assess stress appraisal during the past month and was hosted on Qualtrics. It comprised 14 items to indicate how often participants felt or thought a certain way, for example, ‘In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and “stressed”?’’. Each item uses a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (never) to 4 (very often).

The flanker task (Eriksen & Eriksen, 1974) was hosted on the Millisecond Test Library (see Appendix E) to assess RDI. The task has four target letters (H, K, S, C), the target letter always appears above a fixed cross, to which the participants have to respond as fast as possible without compromising accuracy. When letters ‘H’ or ‘K’ appear, letter Q should be pressed, and when letters ‘S’ or ‘C’ appear, letter P should be pressed. Target letter can appear alone (i.e. H), referring to neutral trials, it can appear with letters from target category (i.e. HHHHH), referring to compatible trials, or it can be flanked by other letters of the other target (i.e. HSHH), referring to incompatible trials. The experiment was presented in Qualtrics.

Procedure

Participants were invited using the Participant Invitation (see Appendix A). It included information regarding study aims, eligibility, data collection, anonymity and confidentiality of participation, withdrawal ability, duration to complete survey was 25-30 mins, location of survey, researcher and supervisor contact details, and link to survey. Once participants clicked

Qualtrics link, Participant Information Sheet (see Appendix B) was presented. The sheet provided participants with a brief overview of study aims, eligibility, data collection and storage, anonymity and confidentiality, withdrawal procedure, contact details of researcher and supervisor, in accordance with ethical guidelines of the British Psychological Society (BPS). Participants were then requested to provide informed consent (see ‘Consent Form’, Appendix C), to confirm they are over 18, with no prior diagnosis of sleep or psychological disorders, and to create a unique ID to be used in case they wish to withdraw.

Next, participants were asked to provide information including: age, gender, education, occupation, chronotype, and type of shiftwork. Participants then had to complete the PSQI (Buysse et al., 1989) and PSS-14 (Cohen et al., 1983). Afterwards, participants were asked to follow a link to the flanker task (Eriksen & Eriksen, 1974) hosted on the Millisecond Test Library. Following the completion of the flanker task, participants returned to Qualtrics and were presented with the Debrief Form (see Appendix D), where they had to re-consent and were provided with contact details of support groups.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to BPS Code Ethics and Conduct (BPS, 2019), the BPS Code of Human Research Ethics (BPS, 2014), and the GDPR (2018) guidelines.

Analytical Strategy

On the PSQI, three participants entered invalid sleep duration; it was estimated based on their answers to questions (i.e. time in bed and how long it takes to fall asleep). Four participants made decimal place errors. 20 participants confused AM for PM or entered minutes instead of hours. For all mentioned participants their scores were matched against their answers in other questions and they were kept in the analysis.

Ten participants used the same ID, it was difficult to match their scores on the flanker task, PSS, and PSQI, they were eliminated from the study. Five participants completed the study twice, only first attempts were included. Three participants were removed from the analysis due to high error rate (around 50%) and their mean RTs were very fast (around 250ms), suggesting they were not engaged in the task.

Between-subjects mean RTs and PEs were examined for extreme scores. Observations further than 3 SD away from the mean were replaced with the respective values (Friedman & Miyake, 2004; Gartner & Strobel, 2021). This affected 1.76% of the trials.

Interference effect was calculated and outliers were identified using 3 SD method. Analysis was run with and without outliers, results remained the same, therefore, outliers were kept in the analysis.

To check data distribution, visual checks of histograms were performed, Z-values of skewness and kurtosis were calculated, Shapiro-Wilk and K-S test were conducted.

Results

Table 1 depicts descriptive statistics and normality tests for shift workers, non-shifts workers, high stress, low stress, good sleep, and bad sleep.

Table 1.

Descriptive Statistics and Normality Tests for Shift, Non-shift, High-stress, Low-stress, Good-sleep, and Poor-sleep Groups

DVs		Non-shift work	Shift work	High stress	Low Stress	Poor Sleep	Good Sleep
M (SD)	BIS _{incom-comp}	-.78 (.85)	-.73 (.81)	-.78 (.81)	-.72 (.84)	-.79 (.91)	-.70 (.71)
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	1.30 (1.07)	1.27 (1.01)	1.29 (.98)	1.27 (1.09)	1.43 (1.10)	1.43 (1.10)

	RT _{incom-comp}	17.56 (26.55)	16.84 (28.29)	19.19 (25.64)	15.28 (28.98)	16.30 (29.70)	18.39 (24.04)
	RT _{incomp-neu}	61.06 (45.52)	52.56 (49.88)	64.23 (48.48)	49.41 (46.49)	60.40 (51.21)	51.43 (42.79)
95% CI lower	BIS _{incom-comp}	-95	-88	-94	-89	-95	-85
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	1.08	1.08	1.10	1.06	1.23	.89
	RT _{incom-comp}	12.26	11.47	14.13	9.72	10.92	13.29
	RT _{incomp-neu}	51.98	43.09	54.66	40.50	51.14	42.37
95% CI upper	BIS _{incom-comp}	-61	-58	-62	-56	-63	-55
Table 1. (continued)							
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	1.51	1.46	1.49	1.48	1.63	1.28
	RT _{incom-comp}	22.85	22.21	24.25	20.83	23.48	21.66
	RT _{incomp-neu}	70.14	62.03	73.80	58.32	69.66	60.50
Skewness (SE)	BIS _{incom-comp}	-1.59 (.24)	-1.52 (.23)	-1.85 (.24)	-1.33 (.23)	-1.53 (.22)	-1.39 (.26)
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	1.94 (.24)	1.83 (.23)	2.27 (.24)	1.62 (.23)	2.10 (.22)	1.22 (.26)
	RT _{incom-comp}	-68 (.24)	-76 (.23)	-29 (.24)	-97 (.23)	-78 (.22)	-47 (.26)
	RT _{incomp-neu}	1.04 (.24)	-1.22 (.23)	.16 (.24)	-.90 (.23)	-1.03 (.22)	1.19 (.26)
Kurtosis (SE)	BIS _{incom-comp}	4.00 (.48)	7.82 (.46)	8.73 (.48)	3.44 (.46)	5.53 (.44)	4.22 (.51)
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	6.90 (.48)	9.08 (.46)	11.17 (.48)	5.75 (.46)	8.80 (.44)	3.16 (.51)
	RT _{incom-comp}	1.89 (.48)	1.37 (.46)	.40 (.48)	2.01 (.46)	1.24 (.51)	1.41 (.44)
	RT _{incomp-neu}	2.76 (.48)	4.58 (.46)	4.63 (.48)	3.63 (.46)	4.24 (.44)	5.35 (.51)
K-S test	BIS _{incom-comp}	.00	.02	.00	.02	.00	.20
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	.00	.08	.00	.02	.00	.02
	RT _{incom-comp}	.061	.01	.20	.00	.01	.20
	RT _{incomp-neu}	.07	.09	.05	.15	.20	.20
S-W test	BIS _{incom-comp}	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
	RT _{incom-comp}	.01	.00	.57	.00	.00	.06
	RT _{incomp-neu}	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Median	BIS _{incom-comp}	-.64	-.70	-.77	-.60	-.73	-.61
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	1.04	1.18	1.11	1.18	1.29	.95
	RT _{incom-comp}	17.58	20.20	20.24	17.58	18.53	19.65
	RT _{incomp-neu}	52.97	55.37	56.49	49.13	59.37	45.88
Range	BIS _{incom-comp}	4.92	6.32	6.32	5.02	6.32	4.48
	BIS _{incomp-neu}	7.41	7.72	7.72	7.41	7.72	5.68

	RT _{incom-comp}	156.66	165.48	134.54	165.48	165.48	137.62
	RT _{incomp-neu}	280.06	339.29	400.72	319.40	359.91	323.23
N	All variables	99	109	101	107	120	88

Data doesn't fall within the +/- 1.96 range necessary to meet assumptions of normality.

The data has a K-S significance value less than 5% ($p < .05$) meaning that the data is not normally distributed. Multiple data transformation methods were applied, such as; log10 and SQRT, data still failed to meet normality assumptions (see Appendix I). Therefore, non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was used.

Interference effect and shiftwork

Interference effect (BIS_{incom-comp}) of non-shift workers ($Mdn = -.64$) were closer to 0 than shift-workers ($Mdn = -.70$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{\text{non-shift workers}} = 99, N_{\text{shift-workers}} = 109) = 5335.00, z = -.14, p = .889$.

Interference effect (BIS_{incomp-neu}) of non-shift workers ($Mdn = 1.04$) were closer to 0 than shift-workers ($Mdn = 1.18$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{\text{non-shift workers}} = 99, N_{\text{shift-workers}} = 109) = 5269.00, z = -.14, P = .770$.

Interference effect (RT_{incom-comp}) of non-shift workers ($Mdn = 17.58$) were lower than shift-workers ($Mdn = 20.20$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{\text{non-shift workers}} = 99, N_{\text{shift-workers}} = 109) = 5312.50, Z = -.19, p = .848$.

Interference effect (RT_{incomp-neu}) of non-shift workers ($Mdn = 52.97$) were lower than shift-workers ($Mdn = 55.37$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{\text{non-shift workers}} = 99, N_{\text{shift-workers}} = 109) = 5156.00, Z = -.55, p = .581$.

Interference effect and stress

Interference effect ($BIS_{incom-comp}$) of low stress ($Mdn = -.60$) were closer to 0 than high stress ($Mdn = -.77$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{low-stress} = 107, N_{high-stress} = 101) = 4996.00, z = -.94, p = .348$.

Interference effect ($BIS_{incomp-neu}$) of low stress ($Mdn = 1.18$) were closer to 0 than high stress ($Mdn = 1.11$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{low-stress} = 107, N_{high-stress} = 101) = 5289.00, z = -.26, p = .792$.

Interference effect ($RT_{incom-comp}$) of low stress ($Mdn = 17.58$) were lower than high stress ($Mdn = 20.24$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{low-stress} = 107, N_{high-stress} = 101) = 5069.00, Z = -.77, p = .441$.

Interference effect ($RT_{incomp-neu}$) of low stress ($Mdn = 49.13$) were lower than high stress ($Mdn = 56.49$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically significant, $U(N_{low-stress} = 107, N_{high-stress} = 101) = 4518.50, z = -2.04, p = .041$.

Interference effect and sleep

Interference effect ($BIS_{incom-comp}$) of good sleepers ($Mdn = -.61$) were closer to 0 than bad sleepers ($Mdn = -.73$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{good-sleepers} = 88, N_{bad-sleepers} = 120) = 4954.00, z = -.76, p = .447$.

Interference effect ($BIS_{incomp-neu}$) of good sleepers ($Mdn = .95$) were lower than bad sleepers ($Mdn = 1.29$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically significant, $U(N_{good-sleepers} = 88, N_{bad-sleepers} = 120) = 4148.000, z = -2.64, p = .008$

Interference effect ($RT_{incom-comp}$) of good sleepers ($Mdn = 19.65$) were higher than bad sleepers ($Mdn = 18.53$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically non-significant, $U(N_{good-sleepers} = 88, N_{bad-sleepers} = 120) = 52225.50, Z = -.13, p = .899$.

Interference effect ($RT_{\text{incomp-neu}}$) of good sleepers ($Mdn = 45.88$) were lower than bad sleepers ($Mdn = 59.37$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically significant, $U(N_{\text{good-sleepers}} = 88, N_{\text{bad-sleepers}} = 120) = 4368.50, z = -2.13, p = .034$.

Table 2.

Mann-Whitney U Test of Interference Effect and PSQI

DV		Work		Stress		Sleep	
		Non-shift	Shift	High stress	Low stress	Good sleep	Bad sleep
Table 2. (continued)							
BIS _{incom-comp}	Mean	105.11	103.94	100.47	108.31	108.20	101.78
	Rank						
	Z		-.14		-.94		-.76
	U		5335.00		4996.00		4954.00
	Sig.		.889		.348		.447
BIS _{incomp-neu}	Mean	103.22	105.66	105.63	103.43	91.64	113.93
	Rank						
	Z		-.29		-.26		-2.64
	U		5269.00		5289.00		4148.00
	Sig.		.770		.792		.008
RT _{incom-comp}	Mean	103.66	105.26	107.81	101.37	105.12	104.05
	Rank						
	Z		-.19		-.77		-.13
	U		5312.500		5069.00		5225.50
	Sig.		.848		.441		.889
RT _{incomp-neu}	Mean	106.92	102.30	113.26	96.23	94.14	112.10
	Rank						
	Z		-.55		-2.04		-2.13
	U		5156.00		4518.500		4368.500
	Sig.		.581		.041		.034
PSQI	Mean	90.24	117.45				
	Rank						
	Z		-3.27				
	U		3984.00				
	Sig.		.001				

A Spearman's rank-order correlation was run to determine the relationship between sleep and stress. There was a strong, positive correlation between these scores, which was statistically significant ($r(206) = .54, p = .000$).

Sleep quality scores of non-shift workers ($Mdn = 5.00$) were lower than shift-workers ($Mdn = 7.00$). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically significant, $U(N_{\text{non-shift workers}} = 99, N_{\text{shift-workers}} = 109) = 3984.00, z = -3.27, p = .001$.

Sleep quality and stress scores of night owls ($Mdn = 6.00$ and 27.00) were higher than early birds ($Mdn = 5.00$ and 24.00). A Mann-Whitney test indicated that this difference was statistically significant, $U(N_{\text{night owls}} = 109, N_{\text{early birds}} = 50) = 1907.50$ and $2177.50, z = -3.05$ and $-2.0233, p = .002$ and $.042$.

Table 3.

Mann-Whitney U Test of sleep and stress in morning-and evening-chronotypes

	Mean Rank		Z	U	Sig.
	Night owls	Early birds			
Sleep	87.50	63.65	-3.05	1907.50	.002
Stress	85.02	69.05	-2.02	2177.50	.042

Discussion

Shiftwork is associated with higher risk of making mistakes on duty, increased accidents (Ruutiainen et al., 2013; Schlick et al., 2020; Suminska et al., 2021), and increased distractibility (Anderson & Horne, 2006; Lee et al., 2015), which is attributed to compromised EFs (Chellappa et al., 2019; Cheng, 2017) and RDI (Esmaily et al. 2021). The current study sought to determine the effects of shiftwork, sleep quality, and stress levels on RDI. Additionally, the effects of chronotypes on stress and sleep were investigated, and the relationship between stress and sleep was explored.

Shiftwork and sleep

The current study findings indicate that shift workers had significantly higher scores on the PSQI than non-shift workers. Shift workers had a PSQI score of seven, while non-shift workers had a score of five. On the PSQI, scores above five are considered clinical sleep problems and reflect poor sleep quality (Buysse et al., 1989). Therefore, the findings of this study indicate that shift workers had poor sleep quality and worse sleep quality compared to non-shift workers. These results may be due to the circadian misalignment and lack of regular night sleep caused by their work schedule demands, as shift workers work outside the typical window of 8 am to 5 pm (McMenamin, 2007), when the body's natural tendency is to sleep. Another reason could be due to reduced melatonin levels, which is prevalent among shift workers (Leung et al., 2016). Reduced melatonin levels may disturb sleep, because melatonin regulates the sleep/wake cycle and helps promote sleep (Pandi-Perumal et al., 2007).

This finding is consistent with that of Elhami Athar et al. (2020), who investigated the effects of shiftwork on sleep quality among university security staff using the PSQI and found night shift workers had poorer sleep quality. However, these results partially contradict Kazemi et al. (2016) study, where there was no significant difference on PSQI scores after day and after night shifts, indicating no effects of shiftwork on sleep quality. The reason for the difference in the results may be due to the study design. In Kazemi et al. (2016) study was within-subject design, where all participants were shift workers, however, the current study compared shift workers and non-shift workers. Although there were no differences after day or night shifts in Kazemi et al. (2016) study, the PSQI score for shift workers was above five, indicating poor sleep quality (Buysse et al., 1989), this is in line with the current study findings.

The current results confirm and extend previous evidence that shiftwork leads to poor sleep quality, not only among night shiftwork security staff as has previously been shown (Elhami Athar et al., 2020), but also among various shift types (i.e. night, rotating) and among different job types (e.g. aged care workers, hotel receptionists, helpline agents, cashiers, airline crew, nurses, military personnel, emergency services, security services, engineers, etc.) as shown in the current study.

Resistance to distractor interference and shiftwork

There was no significant difference between shift and non-shift workers on interference effect measured by $BIS_{incompatible-compatible}$, $BIS_{incompatible-neutral}$, $RT_{incompatible-compatible}$, and $RT_{incompatible-neutral}$. Contrary to expectations, interference effect of shift and non-shift workers was not significantly different on most measures. The reason for the indifference in interference effect between shift and non-shift workers may be due to compensation of cognitive functions. That is when RDI is compromised, other brain regions work to compensate for the loss in order to maintain efficiency. The compensation processes can be explained through cognitive reserve, which refers to the brain's ability to maintain cognitive performance, including executive functions, in the face of cognitive inefficiency due to pathology or age (Stern et al., 2018). These compensatory processes have been demonstrated in inhibitory functions, Ansaldo et al. (2015) found that elderly bilinguals performed same as the monolinguals on inhibition control tasks, however, they recruited different neural substrates, suggesting that compensatory processes took place to make up for the loss in inhibitory functions. This explanation was also put forward by other studies on inhibition control (i.e. Chuah et al., 2006; Glisky et al., 2021). Another explanation for the current results may be that the effects of shiftwork on RDI are not long-lasting, meaning that after shift workers get enough rest their performance on the task improves.

Studies have shown that inhibition control deficits due to sleep deprivation are enhanced after recovery sleep (Jin et al., 2015; Wilckens et al., 2014). This may be a plausible explanation for the current results as the majority of shift workers (82%) in this study did not do the task immediately after their shifts. The majority of measures show that there is no difference in interference effect, it can be concluded that there is not enough evidence in this study to indicate that shiftwork affects RDI, meaning shift work may not lead to increased distractibility.

These results are partially in line with a previous study conducted by McHill and Wright (2019), where they found a significant decrease in the number of correct responses in night-simulated shiftwork compared to day shift, however, RTs were not affected. Similar results were also demonstrated by Elhami Athar et al. (2020) and Esmaily et al. (2021). Nonetheless, these results contradict previous studies by Bartel et al. (2004) and Kaliyaperumal et al. (2017). The difference in the results of the current study and previous studies may be attributed to the different tasks employed. Kaliyaperumal et al. (2017) used the Stroop task, while the current study used the flanker task. These tasks have low correlation (Bender, 2017) and they both recruit different neuronal regions (Nee et al., 2007). Moreover, these tasks tests different subcomponents of inhibition, the Stroop task taps more response inhibition (Miyake et al., 2000), and the flanker task taps more into RDI (Bisset et al., 2009). Another reason for the difference in results may be due to the variability in the jobs of shift workers, Kaliyaperumal et al. (2017) recruited nurse shift workers, while this study recruited shift workers of various jobs.

Resistance to distractor interference and sleep

There was significant difference between good and poor sleepers on interference effect measured using $BIS_{incompatible-neutral}$ scores, and $RT_{incompatible-neutral}$ scores, where poor sleepers had BIS score that was away from the z-score and a larger RT interference effect, indicating less

efficient RDI. There was no significant difference in $RT_{\text{incompatible-compatible}}$ scores and $BIS_{\text{incompatible-compatible}}$ scores between good and poor sleepers. Most measures indicate that good sleepers had more efficient RDI compared to poor sleepers. An interesting pattern has emerged. BIS and RT measures using neutral trials as a baseline yielded same results and measures using compatible trials as a baseline yielded same results. It has been observed that some researchers use compatible trials (Burke et al., 2015; Esmaily et al., 2021; McHill & Wright, 2019), while others use neutral trials (Cain et al., 2011; Gartner & Strobel, 2021; Friedman & Miyake, 2004; McHill & Wright, 2019; Miyake et al., 2000). The neutral trials are sometimes used as the baseline instead of compatible trials avoid the facilitation processes that occur from compatible trials (Rey-Mermet et al., 2018), as the letters in neutral trials are alone and not flanked by any other distractors as the case in compatible trials.

These results are in line with studies investigating the effects of sleep deprivation on inhibition control. Cunningham et al. (2018) found performance deficits on the flanker and the go/nogo tasks after 24 hours of sleep restriction. Similar findings have been reported by Skurvydas et al. (2020), where they found significant drop in performance on the Stroop and go/nogo tasks for both RT and PE after 24 hours of sleep deprivation. The current results are inconsistent with that of Rana et al. (2018). The reason for the inconsistency in the results may be due to the different tasks used. Rana et al. (2018) used the Stroop task, while the present study used the flanker task. As mentioned previously, these two tasks have low correlations (Bender, 2017), and measure different subcomponents of inhibition functions (Bisset et al., 2009; Miyake et al., 2000).

Resistance to distractor interference and stress

There was significant difference between low and high stress groups on interference effect measured using $RT_{\text{incompatible-neutral}}$ scores, where high stress group had larger interference effect, indicating less efficient RDI. There was no significant difference in $BIS_{\text{incompatible-compatible}}$ scores, $BIS_{\text{incompatible-neutral}}$ scores, and $RT_{\text{incompatible-compatible}}$ scores. The majority of measures point toward a non-significant relationship between stress and RDI, indicating that stress levels may not affect RDI, and therefore may not lead to increased distractibility.

The difference in results between RT-based and BIS-based interference effects stresses the point that different measurements of interference effect may lead to contradicting results. And that unless accuracy rate is set to a certain rate (e.g. 90% Bruyer & Brysbaert, 2011), RT-based results may not be accurate and may not be enough to draw conclusions.

The current results contradict the study of Stracke et al. (2016), where they found that induced stress to affect inhibition control using a Stroop task. The reason for the different results could be that in Stracke et al. (2016) study, they have induced stress, while the current study looked at the perceived stress. Moreover, Stracke et al. (2016) used a Stroop task, while the current study used the flanker task.

Stress and sleep

Another finding of the current study was that poor sleep quality was correlated with higher stress levels, indicating that poor sleep quality may increase stress levels and high stress levels may decrease sleep quality. A possible explanation for these results may be because higher perceived stress levels are correlated with higher cortisol levels (van Eck & Nicolson, 1994), which could hinder REM sleep (Vgontzas et al., 2003), and, therefore, decrease sleep quality. These results are in line with previous studies of different populations, where higher stress levels

were correlated with poor sleep quality among medical students (Almojali et al., 2017), police officers (Charles et al., 2011), and nurses (da Rocha et al., 2012).

Chronotypes

An interesting finding of the current study was that night owls scored higher on PSQI and PSS than early birds, suggesting that evening chronotypes have worse sleep quality and higher perceived stress compared to earlier chronotypes. Evening chronotype is correlated with higher stress hormones and sleep apnea (Lucassen et al., 2013), which could increase their perceived stress levels and worsen their sleep quality. In accordance with the present results, previous studies have demonstrated that evening chronotypes had poor sleep quality (Juda et al., 2013; Yun et al., 2015), and more sleep complaints than morning chronotypes (Merkikanto et al., 2012).

Implications

The current findings highlight the alarming effects of shiftwork on sleep quality and that it is poor sleep quality, and not shift work or stress per se, that can jeopardize RDI, which may lead to increased distractibility. These findings have implications for employers of shift workers by implementing measures that minimize the negative consequence of shiftwork on sleep. This can be done by keeping shift schedules consistent (Chang et al., 2011), and by allowing enough rest between shifts (Chang et al., 2014). Also, knowing that attention and executive functions is compromised during night shifts (Chellapa et al., 2019), workers can lighten the workload during night shifts to minimize the risk of making mistakes on duty, which could be risky to the workers and the work environment.

Moreover, the study has implications for shift workers themselves to prioritize their sleep needs over social commitments and take measures that help attenuate shiftwork effects, such as physical activity (Lambiase et al., 2014).

Limitations

The current study did not control for time of testing, which is known to affect inhibition control performance (Borella et al., 2011), suggesting that it is best to test participants at the same time of the day. Also, The study did not control for the number of consecutive night shifts performed by workers. A possible adaptation can happen after certain number of consecutive night shifts (Chang et al., 2011), which may lead to enhanced performance. Another limitation to this study was the participants' length of service, which varied from one year to over 15 years. Knowing that the vulnerability to shiftwork increases with longer service duration (Bokenberger et al., 2018; Brown et al., 2009; Marquie et al., 2015), it is possible that participants with less experience may outperform those serving over 15 years, therefore, is best to recruit participants with similar service length.

Future direction and recommendations

Thus, future work should take into consideration the duration of work experience, which can impact the vulnerability to shiftwork consequences, it would be informative to investigate the effects of shiftwork on RDI in a population with similar work experience length.

The debate around the separability of response inhibition and RDI is still ongoing (i.e. Bisset et al., 2009; Friedman & Miyake, 2004). Future research should look into response inhibition and RDI separately in shiftwork population to see whether it may affect these two functions differently. However, it is important that researchers use a task which taps into the specific inhibition function to be tested. While inhibition task impurity is unavoidable (Friedman

& Miyake, 2004), the flanker task tests RDI (Bisset et al., 2009), and is less susceptible to task impurity (Forstmann et al., 2008). As for response inhibition, many tasks may be used, such as Stop-signal task (Logan, 1994). However, the Stroop task may be best avoided when the interest is to tease the difference between response inhibition and RDI, that is because the Stroop task can tap into both response inhibition (Miyake et al., 2000), and selective attention (Bender, 2017), and it is more sensitive to task impurity (Forstmann et al., 2008).

Strengths

One of the strengths of this study is that participants varied in occupation (e.g. aged care workers, hotel receptionists, helpline agents, cashiers, airline crew, nurses, military personnel, emergency services, security services, engineers, etc.), age, gender, and shift types (including night shifts and rotating shifts), this along with the sample size makes the results more generalizable to a larger population compared to previous research.

This study was a between-subject design, where participants performed the task once, preserving the novelty of the task and eliminating practice improvement effects, that are common in RT-based tasks (Wostmann et al., 2013). Also, this is the first study to use BIS scores to measure interference effect in a shiftwork population, eliminating SATs effects (Liesefeld & Janczyk, 2019).

Conclusion

The current study was set to investigate the effects of shiftwork, sleep quality, and stress levels on RDI. Additionally, the effects of chronotypes on stress and sleep were examined, and the relationship between stress and sleep was explored. Taken together, the results of the current research indicate that shiftwork negatively impacts sleep quality and that poor sleep quality is linked to increased distractibility, which can jeopardize individuals' health and put the work

environment at risk. However, there is not enough evidence in this study to indicate that shiftwork or stress affect RDI, implying that shiftwork and stress do not directly influence distractibility. Other findings in this study indicate that evening chronotypes have higher stress levels and poorer sleep quality than day chronotypes, and that increased stress can lead to poor sleep quality and vice versa.

References

- Adams, T. & Venter, S. (2021). All night long: an assessment of the cognitive effects of night shift work in anaesthesiology trainees. *Southern African Journal of Anaesthesia and Analgesia*, 26(6), 287-292. <https://doi.org/10.36303/SAJAA.2020.26.6.2361>
- Almojali, A. I., Almalki, S. A., Alothman, A. S., Masuadi, E. M., & Alaqeel, M. K. (2017). The prevalence and association of stress with sleep quality among medical students. *Journal of epidemiology and global health*, 7(3), 169–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jegh.2017.04.005>
- Andersen, P., Skogli, E., Hovik, K., & Egeland, J. & Øie, M. (2015). Associations Among Symptoms of Autism, Symptoms of Depression and Executive Functions in Children with High-Functioning Autism: A 2 Year Follow-Up Study. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 45(8). 10.1007/s10803-015-2415-8.
- Anderson, C., & Horne, J. A. (2006). Sleepiness enhances distraction during a monotonous task. *Sleep*, 29(4), 573–576. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sleep/29.4.573>
- Anderson, C., & Platten, C. R. (2011). Sleep deprivation lowers inhibition and enhances impulsivity to negative stimuli. *Behavioural Brain Research*, 217(2), 463–466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbr.2010.09.020>
- Anderson, C., Sullivan, J. P., Flynn-Evans, E. E., Cade, B. E., Czeisler, C. A., & Lockley, S. W. (2012). Deterioration of neurobehavioral performance in resident physicians during repeated exposure to extended duration work shifts. *Sleep*, 35(8), 1137–1146. <https://doi.org/10.5665/sleep.2004>

- Ansaldò, A. I., Ghazi-Saidi, L., & Adrover-Roig, D. (2015). Interference Control In Elderly Bilinguals: Appearances Can Be Misleading. *Journal of clinical and experimental neuropsychology*, 37(5), 455–470. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803395.2014.990359>
- Ardila, A., Rosselli, M., Matute, E., & Guajardo, S. (2005). The influence of the parents' educational level on the development of executive functions. *Developmental neuropsychology*, 28(1), 539–560. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326942dn2801_5
- Aron A. R. (2007). The neural basis of inhibition in cognitive control. *The Neuroscientist : a review journal bringing neurobiology, neurology and psychiatry*, 13(3), 214–228. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073858407299288>
- Baddeley, A. D. (1983). Working Memory. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences*, 302(1110), 311–324. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2395996>
- Bartel, P., Offermeier, W., Smith, F., & Becker, P. (2004). Attention and working memory in resident anaesthetists after night duty: group and individual effects. *Occupational and environmental medicine*, 61(2), 167–170. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.2002.006197>
- Basner, M., Rubinstein, J., Fomberstein, K. M., Coble, M. C., Ecker, A., Avinash, D., & Dinges, D. F. (2008). Effects of night work, sleep loss and time on task on simulated threat detection performance. *Sleep*, 31(9), 1251–1259.
- Bender, A. (2017). *Selecting and inhibiting responses: Common cognitive and neural substrates?*. [PhD Thesis, School of Psychology, The University of Queensland]. UQ eSpace. <https://doi.org/10.14264/uq1.2018.61>

- Bissett, P. G., Nee, D. E., & Jonides, J. (2009). Dissociating interference-control processes between memory and response. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 35(5), 1306–1316. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0016537>
- Bokenberger, K., Sjölander, A., Dahl Aslan, A. K., Karlsson, I. K., Åkerstedt, T., & Pedersen, N. L. (2018). Shift work and risk of incident dementia: a study of two population-based cohorts. *European journal of epidemiology*, 33(10), 977–987. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-018-0430-8>
- Borella, E., Ludwig, C., Dirk, J., & de Ribaupierre, A. (2011). The influence of time of testing on interference, working memory, processing speed, and vocabulary: age differences in adulthood. *Experimental aging research*, 37(1), 76–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0361073X.2011.536744>
- British Psychological Society. (2014). *BPS Code of Human Research Ethics* (2nd ed.). <https://www.bps.org.uk/news-and-policy/bps-code-human-research-ethics-2nd-edition-2014>
- Brown, D. L., Feskanich, D., Sánchez, B. N., Rexrode, K. M., Schernhammer, E. S., & Lisabeth, L. D. (2009). Rotating night shift work and the risk of ischemic stroke. *American journal of epidemiology*, 169(11), 1370–1377. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwp056>
- Bruyer, R., & Brysbaert, M. (2011). Combining speed and accuracy in cognitive psychology: is the Inverse Efficiency Score (IES) a better dependent variable than the mean Reaction Time (RT) and the Percentage of Errors (PE)? *PSYCHOLOGICA BELGICA*, 51(1), 5–13.
- Brydges, C. R., Clunies-Ross, K., Clohessy, M., Lo, Z. L., Nguyen, A., Rousset, C., Whitelaw, P., Yeap, Y. J., & Fox, A. M. (2012). Dissociable components of cognitive control: an

- event-related potential (ERP) study of response inhibition and interference suppression. *PloS one*, 7(3), e34482. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0034482>
- Brydges, C. R., Anderson, M., Reid, C. L., & Fox, A. M. (2013). Maturation of cognitive control: delineating response inhibition and interference suppression. *PloS one*, 8(7), e69826. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0069826>
- Burke, T. M., Scheer, F., Ronda, J. M., Czeisler, C. A., & Wright, K. P., Jr (2015). Sleep inertia, sleep homeostatic and circadian influences on higher-order cognitive functions. *Journal of sleep research*, 24(4), 364–371. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jsr.12291>
- Buysse, D. J., Reynolds, C. F., 3rd, Monk, T. H., Berman, S. R., & Kupfer, D. J. (1989). The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index: a new instrument for psychiatric practice and research. *Psychiatry research*, 28(2), 193–213. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781\(89\)90047-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781(89)90047-4)
- Cain, S. W., Silva, E. J., Chang, A. M., Ronda, J. M., & Duffy, J. F. (2011). One night of sleep deprivation affects reaction time, but not interference or facilitation in a Stroop task. *Brain and cognition*, 76(1), 37–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2011.03.005>
- Chang, Y. S., Wu, Y. H., Hsu, C. Y., Tang, S. H., Yang, L. L., & Su, S. F. (2011). Impairment of perceptual and motor abilities at the end of a night shift is greater in nurses working fast rotating shifts. *Sleep medicine*, 12(9), 866–869. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2011.03.018>
- Chang, Y. S., Chen, H. L., Wu, Y. H., Hsu, C. Y., Liu, C. K., & Hsu, C. (2014). Rotating night shifts too quickly may cause anxiety and decreased attentional performance, and impact prolactin levels during the subsequent day: a case control study. *BMC psychiatry*, 14, 218. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-014-0218-7>

- Charles, L. E., Slaven, J. E., Mnatsakanova, A., Ma, C., Violanti, J. M., Fekedulegn, D., Andrew, M. E., Vila, B. J., & Burchfiel, C. M. (2011). Association of perceived stress with sleep duration and sleep quality in police officers. *International journal of emergency mental health, 13*(4), 229–241.
- Chellappa, S. L., Morris, C. J., & Scheer, F. (2019). Effects of circadian misalignment on cognition in chronic shift workers. *Scientific reports, 9*(1), 699. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-36762-w>
- Cheng, P., Tallent, G., Bender, T. J., Tran, K. M., & Drake, C. L. (2017). Shift Work and Cognitive Flexibility: Decomposing Task Performance. *Journal of biological rhythms, 32*(2), 143–153. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0748730417699309>
- Cho, K., Ennaceur, A., Cole, J. C., & Suh, C. K. (2000). Chronic jet lag produces cognitive deficits. *The Journal of neuroscience : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience, 20*(6), RC66. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.20-06-j0005.2000>
- Chuah, Y. M., Venkatraman, V., Dinges, D. F., & Chee, M. W. (2006). The neural basis of interindividual variability in inhibitory efficiency after sleep deprivation. *The Journal of neuroscience : the official journal of the Society for Neuroscience, 26*(27), 7156–7162. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0906-06.2006>
- Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A Global Measure of Perceived Stress. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior, 24*(4), 385–396. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2136404>
- Cohen, S., & Williamson, G. (1988). Perceived Stress in a Probability Sample of the United States. In S. Spacapan, & S. Oskamp (Eds.), *The Social Psychology of Health: Claremont Symposium on Applied Social Psychology* (pp. 31-67). Newbury Park, CA: Sage.

- Cummings, J. L., & Miller, B. L. (2007). *Conceptual and clinical aspects of the frontal lobes*. In B. L. Miller & J. L. Cummings (Eds.), *The human frontal lobes: Functions and disorders* (p. 12–21). The Guilford Press.
- Cunningham, J., Jones, S., Eskes, G. A., & Rusak, B. (2018). Acute Sleep Restriction Has Differential Effects on Components of Attention. *Frontiers in psychiatry, 9*, 499. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2018.00499>
- da Rocha, M. C., & De Martino, M. M. (2010). O estresse e qualidade de sono do enfermeiro nos diferentes turnos hospitalares [Stress and sleep quality of nurses working different hospital shifts]. *Revista da Escola de Enfermagem da U S P, 44*(2), 280–286. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0080-62342010000200006>
- Deary, I. J., & Tait, R. (1987). Effects of sleep disruption on cognitive performance and mood in medical house officers. *British medical journal (Clinical research ed.), 295*(6612), 1513–1516. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.295.6612.1513>
- Delis, D., Kaplan, E., & Kramer, N. (2001). Delis–Kaplan executive function system. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t15082-000>
- Diamond A. (2013). Executive functions. *Annual review of psychology, 64*, 135–168. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-113011-143750>
- Draheim, C., Hicks, K. L., & Engle, R. W. (2016). Combining Reaction Time and Accuracy: The Relationship Between Working Memory Capacity and Task Switching as a Case Example. *Perspectives on psychological science : a journal of the Association for Psychological Science, 11*(1), 133–155. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691615596990>

- Draheim, C., Mashburn, C. A., Martin, J. D., & Engle, R. W. (2019). Reaction time in differential and developmental research: A review and commentary on the problems and alternatives. *Psychological bulletin*, *145*(5), 508–535. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000192>
- Drummond, S. P., Paulus, M. P., & Tapert, S. F. (2006). Effects of two nights sleep deprivation and two nights recovery sleep on response inhibition. *Journal of sleep research*, *15*(3), 261–265. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2869.2006.00535.x>
- Elhami Athar M., Atef Vahid, M. K. & Ashouri, A. (2020). The Influence of Shift Work on the Quality of Sleep and Executive Functions. *Journal of Circadian Rhythms*, *18*(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jcr.194>
- Eriksen, B.A., Eriksen, C.W. (1974). Effects of noise letters upon the identification of a target letter in a nonsearch task. *Perception & Psychophysics*, *16*, 143–149. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03203267>
- Esmaily, A., Jambarsang, S., Mohammadian, F., & Mehrparvar, A. H. (2021). Effect of shift work on working memory, attention and response time in nurses. *International journal of occupational safety and ergonomics : JOSE*, 1–6. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2020.1863656>
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Buchner, A., & Lang, A. G. (2009). Statistical power analyses using G*Power 3.1: tests for correlation and regression analyses. *Behavior research methods*, *41*(4), 1149–1160. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BRM.41.4.1149>
- Fisk, J. E., & Sharp, C. A. (2004). Age-related impairment in executive functioning: updating, inhibition, shifting, and access. *Journal of clinical and experimental neuropsychology*, *26*(7), 874–890. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803390490510680>

- Forstmann, B. U., van den Wildenberg, W. P., & Ridderinkhof, K. R. (2008). Neural mechanisms, temporal dynamics, and individual differences in interference control. *Journal of cognitive neuroscience*, 20(10), 1854–1865. <https://doi.org/10.1162/jocn.2008.20122>
- Friedman, N. P., & Miyake, A. (2004). The relations among inhibition and interference control functions: a latent-variable analysis. *Journal of experimental psychology. General*, 133(1), 101–135. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.133.1.101>
- Friedman, N. P., Miyake, A., Young, S. E., DeFries, J. C., Corley, R. P., & Hewitt, J. K. (2008). Individual differences in executive functions are almost entirely genetic in origin. *Journal of experimental psychology. General*, 137(2), 201–225. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.137.2.201>
- Gärtner, A., & Strobel, A. (2021). Individual Differences in Inhibitory Control: A latent Variable Analysis. *Journal of cognition*, 4(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.5334/joc.150>
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). (2018). General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Available at <https://gdpr-info.eu/> (Accessed: 21 March 2021).
- Geurts, H. M., van den Bergh, S. F. W. M., & Ruzzano, L. (2014). Prepotent response inhibition and interference control in autism spectrum disorders: two meta-analyses. *Autism Research*, 7(4), 407-420. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aur.1369>
- Glisky, E., Alexander, G., Hou, M., Kawa, K., Woolverton, C., Zigman, E., Nguyen, L., Haws, K., Figueredo, A. & Ryan, L. (2021) Differences between young and older adults in unity and diversity of executive functions, *Aging, Neuropsychology, and Cognition*, 28:6, 829-854, DOI: [10.1080/13825585.2020.1830936](https://doi.org/10.1080/13825585.2020.1830936)

- Gorfein, D., & MacLeod, C. (Eds). (2007). *Inhibition of Cognition*. American Psychological Association.
- Harnishfeger, K. K. (1995). The development of cognitive inhibition. In *Interference and inhibition in cognition* (pp. 175–204). Elsevier. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012208930-5/50007-6>
- Horne J. (2012). Working throughout the night: beyond 'sleepiness'--impairments to critical decision making. *Neuroscience and biobehavioral reviews*, 36(10), 2226–2231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2012.08.005>
- Hughes, M. M., Linck, J. A., Bowles, A. R., Koeth, J. T., & Bunting, M. F. (2014). Alternatives to switch-cost scoring in the task-switching paradigm: their reliability and increased validity. *Behavior research methods*, 46(3), 702–721. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-013-0411-5>
- Jin, X., Ye, E., Qi, J., Wang, L., Lei, Y., Chen, P., Mi, G., Zou, F., Shao, Y., & Yang, Z. (2015). Recovery Sleep Reverses Impaired Response Inhibition due to Sleep Restriction: Evidence from a Visual Event Related Potentials Study. *PloS one*, 10(12), e0142361. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0142361>
- Juda, M., Vetter, C., & Roenneberg, T. (2013). Chronotype modulates sleep duration, sleep quality, and social jet lag in shift-workers. *Journal of biological rhythms*, 28(2), 141–151. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0748730412475042>
- Kaliyaperumal, D., Elango, Y., Alagesan, M., & Santhanakrishanan, I. (2017). Effects of Sleep Deprivation on the Cognitive Performance of Nurses Working in Shift. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research : JCDR*, 11(8), CC01–CC03. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2017/26029.10324>

- Kane, M. J., Meier, M. E., Smeekens, B. A., Gross, G. M., Chun, C. A., Silvia, P. J., & Kwapil, T. R. (2016). Individual differences in the executive control of attention, memory, and thought, and their associations with schizotypy. *Journal of experimental psychology. General*, 145(8), 1017–1048. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000184>
- Karlsson, B., Knutsson, A., & Lindahl, B. (2001). Is there an association between shift work and having a metabolic syndrome? Results from a population based study of 27,485 people. *Occupational and environmental medicine*, 58(11), 747–752. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.58.11.747>
- Kazemi, R., Haidarimoghadam, R., Motamedzadeh, M., Golmohamadi, R., Soltanian, A., & Zoghipaydar, M. R. (2016). Effects of Shift Work on Cognitive Performance, Sleep Quality, and Sleepiness among Petrochemical Control Room Operators. *Journal of circadian rhythms*, 14, 1. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jcr.134>
- Klingberg, T., Fernell, E., Olesen, P. J., Johnson, M., Gustafsson, P., Dahlström, K., Gillberg, C. G., Forssberg, H., & Westerberg, H. (2005). Computerized training of working memory in children with ADHD--a randomized, controlled trial. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 44(2), 177–186. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-200502000-00010>
- Korko, M., Coulson, M., Jones, A. & Davies, P. (2021). Types of interference and their resolution in monolingual word production. *Acta Psychologica*, 214, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2021.103251>.
- Kwak, K., Kim, B. K., Jang, T. W., Sim, C. S., Ahn, Y. S., Choi, K. S., & Jeong, K. S. (2020). Association between Shift Work and Neurocognitive Function among Firefighters in

- South Korea: A Prospective Before-After Study. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(13), 4647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134647>
- Lambiase, M. J., Gabriel, K. P., Kuller, L. H., & Matthews, K. A. (2014). Sleep and executive function in older women: the moderating effect of physical activity. *The journals of gerontology. Series A, Biological sciences and medical sciences*, 69(9), 1170–1176. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glu038>
- Le Berre, A. P., Fama, R., & Sullivan, E. V. (2017). Executive Functions, Memory, and Social Cognitive Deficits and Recovery in Chronic Alcoholism: A Critical Review to Inform Future Research. *Alcoholism, clinical and experimental research*, 41(8), 1432–1443. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acer.13431>
- Lee, J., Manousakis, J., Fielding, J., & Anderson, C. (2015). Alcohol and sleep restriction combined reduces vigilant attention, whereas sleep restriction alone enhances distractibility. *Sleep*, 38(5), 765–775. <https://doi.org/10.5665/sleep.4672>
- Leung, M., Tranmer, J., Hung, E., Korsiak, J., Day, A. G., & Aronson, K. J. (2016). Shift Work, Chronotype, and Melatonin Patterns among Female Hospital Employees on Day and Night Shifts. *Cancer epidemiology, biomarkers & prevention : a publication of the American Association for Cancer Research, cosponsored by the American Society of Preventive Oncology*, 25(5), 830–838. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-15-1178>
- Lezak, M.D. (1982). The Problem of Assessing Executive Functions. *International Journal of Psychology*, 17, 281-297. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207598208247445>
- Liesefeld, H. R., Fu, X., & Zimmer, H. D. (2015). Fast and careless or careful and slow? Apparent holistic processing in mental rotation is explained by speed–accuracy trade-

- offs. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 41, 1140–1151. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1037/xlm0000081>
- Liesefeld, H. R., & Janczyk, M. (2019). Combining speed and accuracy to control for speed-accuracy trade-offs(?). *Behavior research methods*, 51(1), 40–60. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-018-1076-x>
- Liesefeld, H. R., Liesefeld, A. M., Müller, H. J., & Rangelov, D. (2017). Saliency maps for finding changes in visual scenes?. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, 79, 2190–2201. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-017-1383-9>
- Logan, G. D. (1994). On the ability to inhibit thought and action: A user's guide to the stop signal paradigm. In D. Dagenbach & T. H. Carr (Eds.), *Inhibitory processes in attention, memory, and language* (pp. 189–239). San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- Lucassen, E. A., Zhao, X., Rother, K. I., Mattingly, M. S., Courville, A. B., de Jonge, L., Csako, G., Cizza, G., & Sleep Extension Study Group (2013). Evening chronotype is associated with changes in eating behavior, more sleep apnea, and increased stress hormones in short sleeping obese individuals. *PloS one*, 8(3), e56519. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0056519>
- Lustig, C., Hasher, L., & Zacks, R. T. (2007). Inhibitory deficit theory: Recent developments in a "new view" In D. S. Gorfein & C. M. MacLeod (Eds.), *Inhibition in cognition* (pp. 145–162). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/11587-008>
- Marquié, J. C., Tucker, P., Folkard, S., Gentil, C., & Ansiau, D. (2015). Chronic effects of shift work on cognition: findings from the VISAT longitudinal study. *Occupational and environmental medicine*, 72(4), 258–264. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2013-101993>

- McHill, A. W., & Wright, K. P., Jr (2019). Cognitive Impairments during the Transition to Working at Night and on Subsequent Night Shifts. *Journal of biological rhythms*, 34(4), 432–446. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0748730419848552>
- McMenamin, T. (2007). A time to work: recent trends in shift work and flexible schedules. *Monthly Labor Review*, 130(12), 3–15. <https://www.bls.gov/opub/mlr/2007/12/art1full.pdf>
- Miyake, A., Friedman, N. P., Emerson, M. J., Witzki, A. H., Howerter, A., & Wager, T. D. (2000). The unity and diversity of executive functions and their contributions to complex "Frontal Lobe" tasks: a latent variable analysis. *Cognitive psychology*, 41(1), 49–100. <https://doi.org/10.1006/cogp.1999.0734>
- Morales, J., Yáñez, A., Fernández-González, L., Montesinos-Magraner, L., Marco-Ahulló, A., Solana-Tramunt, M., & Calvete, E. (2019). Stress and autonomic response to sleep deprivation in medical residents: A comparative cross-sectional study. *PloS one*, 14(4), e0214858. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0214858>
- Moran, S., & Gardner, H. (2018). Hill, skill, and will: executive function from a multiple-intelligences perspective. In L. Meltzer (Ed.), *Executive function in education: From theory to practice* (pp. 25–56). The Guilford Press.
- Nabe-Nielsen, K., Hansen, Å. M., Ishtiak-Ahmed, K., Grynderup, M. B., Gyntelberg, F., Islamoska, S., Mortensen, E. L., Phung, T., Rod, N. H., Waldemar, G., Westendorp, R., & Garde, A. H. (2019). Night shift work, long working hours and dementia: a longitudinal study of the Danish Work Environment Cohort Study. *BMJ open*, 9(5), e027027. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-027027>

- Nee, D. E., Wager, T. D., & Jonides, J. (2007). Interference resolution: insights from a meta-analysis of neuroimaging tasks. *Cognitive, affective & behavioral neuroscience*, 7(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3758/cabn.7.1.1>
- Nigg J. T. (2000). On inhibition/disinhibition in developmental psychopathology: views from cognitive and personality psychology and a working inhibition taxonomy. *Psychological bulletin*, 126(2), 220–246. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.126.2.220>
- Nigg J. T. (2001). Is ADHD a disinhibitory disorder?. *Psychological bulletin*, 127(5), 571–598. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.127.5.571>
- Nigg, J. T., Wong, M. M., Martel, M. M., Jester, J. M., Puttler, L. I., Glass, J. M., Adams, K. M., Fitzgerald, H. E., & Zucker, R. A. (2006). Poor response inhibition as a predictor of problem drinking and illicit drug use in adolescents at risk for alcoholism and other substance use disorders. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 45(4), 468–475. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.chi.0000199028.76452.a9>
- Norman, D. A., & Shallice, T. (1980). Attention to action: Willed and automatic control of behavior. 8006, Center for Human Information Processing, California. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED205562>
- O'Hagan, A.D., Issartel, J., Wall, A., Dunne, F., Boylan, P., Groeneweg, J., Herring, M., Campbell, M. & Warrington, G. (2019). Flying on empty: effects of sleep deprivation on pilot performance. *Biological Rhythm Research*, 51(7), 1-22. [10.1080/09291016.2019.1581481](https://doi.org/10.1080/09291016.2019.1581481)
- Pandi-Perumal, S. R., Srinivasan, V., Spence, D. W., & Cardinali, D. P. (2007). Role of the melatonin system in the control of sleep: therapeutic implications. *CNS drugs*, 21(12), 995–1018. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00023210-200721120-00004>

- Pauls, L. J., & Archibald, L. M. (2016). Executive Functions in Children With Specific Language Impairment: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of speech, language, and hearing research : JSLHR*, 59(5), 1074–1086. https://doi.org/10.1044/2016_JSLHR-L-15-0174
- Posner, M. I., & DiGirolamo, G. J. (1998). Executive attention: Conflict, target detection, and cognitive control. In R. Parasuraman (Ed.), *The attentive brain* (pp. 401–423). The MIT Press.
- Rabbitt, P. (1997). Introduction: Methodologies and models in the study of executive function. In P. Rabbitt (Ed.), *Methodology of frontal and executive function* (pp. 1–38). Psychology Press Publishers.
- Rana, B. K., Panizzon, M. S., Franz, C. E., Spoon, K. M., Jacobson, K. C., Xian, H., Ancoli-Israel, S., Lyons, M., & Kremen, W. S. (2018). Association of Sleep Quality on Memory-Related Executive Functions in Middle Age. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society : JINS*, 24(1), 67–76. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355617717000637>
- Rey-Mermet, A., Gade, M., & Oberauer, K. (2018). Should we stop thinking about inhibition? Searching for individual and age differences in inhibition ability. *Journal of experimental psychology. Learning, memory, and cognition*, 44(4), 501–526. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xlm0000450>
- Ruutiainen, A. T., Durand, D. J., Scanlon, M. H., & Itri, J. N. (2013). Increased error rates in preliminary reports issued by radiology residents working more than 10 consecutive hours overnight. *Academic radiology*, 20(3), 305–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acra.2012.09.028>

- Schlick, C., Hewitt, D. B., Quinn, C. M., Ellis, R. J., Shapiro, K. E., Jones, A., Bilimoria, K. Y., & Yang, A. D. (2020). A National Survey of Motor Vehicle Crashes Among General Surgery Residents. *Annals of surgery*, 10.1097/SLA.0000000000003729. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SLA.0000000000003729>
- Schneider, W., & Shiffrin, R. M. (1977). Controlled and automatic human information processing: I. Detection, search, and attention. *Psychological Review*, 84(1), 1–66. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.84.1.1>
- Shields, G. S., Sazma, M. A., & Yonelinas, A. P. (2016). The effects of acute stress on core executive functions: A meta-analysis and comparison with cortisol. *Neuroscience and biobehavioral reviews*, 68, 651–668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2016.06.038>
- Skurvydas, A., Zlibinaite, L., Solianik, R., Brazaitis, M., Valanciene, D., Baranauskiene, N., Majauskiene, D., Mickeviciene, D., Venckunas, T., & Kamandulis, S. (2020). One night of sleep deprivation impairs executive function but does not affect psychomotor or motor performance. *Biology of sport*, 37(1), 7–14. <https://doi.org/10.5114/biol sport.2020.89936>
- Stahl, C., Voss, A., Schmitz, F., Nuszbaum, M., Tüscher, O., Lieb, K., & Klauer, K. C. (2014). Behavioral components of impulsivity. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 143(2), 850–886. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033981>
- Stern, Y., Gazes, Y., Razlighi, Q., Steffener, J., & Habeck, C. (2018). A task-invariant cognitive reserve network. *NeuroImage*, 178, 36–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.05.033>
- Sumińska, S., Nowak, K., Łukomska, B., & Cygan, H. B. (2021). Cognitive functions of shift workers: paramedics and firefighters - an electroencephalography study. *International*

- journal of occupational safety and ergonomics : JOSE*, 27(3), 686–697. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2020.1773117>
- Tiego, J., Testa, R., Bellgrove, M. A., Pantelis, C., & Whittle, S. (2018). A Hierarchical Model of Inhibitory Control. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1339. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01339>
- Titova, O. E., Lindberg, E., Elmståhl, S., Lind, L., Schiöth, H. B., & Benedict, C. (2016). Association between shift work history and performance on the trail making test in middle-aged and elderly humans: the EpiHealth study. *Neurobiology of aging*, 45, 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2016.05.007>
- Torquati, L., Mielke, G. I., Brown, W. J., Burton, N. W., & Kolbe-Alexander, T. L. (2019). Shift Work and Poor Mental Health: A Meta-Analysis of Longitudinal Studies. *American journal of public health*, 109(11), e13–e20. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2019.305278>
- Townsend, J. T., & Ashby, F. G. (1983). Stochastic modelling of elementary psychological processes. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. (2019, September, 24). *Job Flexibilities and Work Schedules -- 2017-2018: Data From The American Time Use Survey*. <https://www.bls.gov/news.release/flex2.nr0.htm>
- Vandierendonck A. (2017). A comparison of methods to combine speed and accuracy measures of performance: A rejoinder on the binning procedure. *Behavior research methods*, 49(2), 653–673. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-016-0721-5>
- Vandierendonck A. (2021). On the Utility of Integrated Speed-Accuracy Measures when Speed-Accuracy Trade-off is Present. *Journal of cognition*, 4(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.5334/joc.154>

- van Eck, M. M., & Nicolson, N. A. (1994). Perceived stress and salivary cortisol in daily life. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine, 16*(3), 221–227.
- Verbruggen, F., Liefoghe, B., & Vandierendonck, A. (2004). The interaction between stop signal inhibition and distractor interference in the flanker and Stroop task. *Acta psychologica, 116*(1), 21–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2003.12.011>
- Verbruggen, F., Liefoghe, B., & Vandierendonck, A. (2006). The effect of interference in the early processing stages on response inhibition in the stop signal task. *Quarterly journal of experimental psychology (2006), 59*(1), 190–203. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17470210500151386>
- Vgontzas, A. N., Zoumakis, M., Bixler, E. O., Lin, H. M., Prolo, P., Vela-Bueno, A., Kales, A., & Chrousos, G. P. (2003). Impaired nighttime sleep in healthy old versus young adults is associated with elevated plasma interleukin-6 and cortisol levels: physiologic and therapeutic implications. *The Journal of clinical endocrinology and metabolism, 88*(5), 2087–2095. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2002-021176>
- von Bastian, C., Blais, C., Brewer, G., Gyurkovics, M., Hedge, C., Kałamała, P., Meier, M., Oberauer, K., Rey-Mermet, A., Rouder, J., Souza, A., Bartsch, L., Conway, A., Draheim, C., Engle, R., Friedman, N., Frischkorn, G., Gustavson, D., Koch, I... Wiemers, E. A. (2020). Advancing the understanding of individual differences in attentional control: Theoretical, methodological, and analytical considerations. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/x3b9k>
- Wilckens, K. A., Woo, S. G., Kirk, A. R., Erickson, K. I., & Wheeler, M. E. (2014). Role of sleep continuity and total sleep time in executive function across the adult lifespan. *Psychology and aging, 29*(3), 658–665. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0037234>

- Woltz, D. J., & Was, C. A. (2006). Availability of related long-term memory during and after attention focus in working memory. *Memory & Cognition*, 34, 668–684. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193587>
- Wöstmann, N. M., Aichert, D. S., Costa, A., Rubia, K., Möller, H. J., & Ettinger, U. (2013). Reliability and plasticity of response inhibition and interference control. *Brain and cognition*, 81(1), 82–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2012.09.010>
- Xie, L., Ren, M., Cao, B., & Li, F. (2017). Distinct brain responses to different inhibitions: Evidence from a modified Flanker Task. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1). [10.1038/s41598-017-04907-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-04907-y)
- Yun, J. A., Ahn, Y. S., Jeong, K. S., Joo, E. J., & Choi, K. S. (2015). The Relationship between Chronotype and Sleep Quality in Korean Firefighters. *Clinical psychopharmacology and neuroscience : the official scientific journal of the Korean College of Neuropsychopharmacology*, 13(2), 201–208. <https://doi.org/10.9758/cpn.2015.13.2.201>
- Zhao, X. C., Han, K. Y., Gao, Y. Y., Li, N., Wang, L., Yu, L. L., Song, M., & Wang, X. Y. (2021). Effects of shift work on sleep and cognitive function among male miners. *Psychiatry research*, 297, 113716. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2021.113716>

Appendix A

Participant Invitation

My name is Fatima Qatami, I am a student at the University of Derby MSc Psychology Programme. I am looking for participants to take part in a study investigating the effects of sleep and stress on interference control among shift and non-shift workers. This study is being supervised by Dr. Hettie Roebuck.

Taking part involves participating in a survey which may last approximately 25 minutes. The survey will take place online at a time to suit you. Your participation will remain confidential and anonymous and is completely voluntary, you can take breaks throughout most parts of the survey. You may also withdraw from the research after participation. There is no obligation to participate.

To take part you must meet the following criteria:

- Be over 18 years old, and
- Free from diagnosed sleep and psychological disorders

Please click the link below to access the survey:

https://derby.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_bINwv8QQyNABRQy

If you would like more information please contact Fatima Qatami on

F.Qatami@unimail.derby.ac.uk or Dr. Hettie Roebuck, H.Roebuck@derby.ac.uk, +44 (0)1332 593876.

Appendix B

Information Sheet

The Effects of Sleep and Stress on Interference Control Among Shift and Non-Shift Workers

My name is Fatima Qatami and I am an MSc Psychology student at the University of Derby. I am currently researching the effect of sleep and stress on interference control among shift and non-shift workers. I am inviting you to take part in a study which will form part of my module studies.

Before you decide if you would like to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully. If anything is not clear and you would like some more information you can get in touch with me on the details below. Please take your time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

The purpose of the study:

The study looks at the effect of sleep and stress on interference control among shift and non-shift workers

Why have I been chosen to take part?

You will have been selected to take part if you are over 18 years old and free from any diagnosed sleep or psychological disorders.

Do I have to take part?

No, it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to take part you will be asked to keep this information sheet and to complete a consent form, which says you are happy to take part. If you decide to take part you are free to withdraw (stop taking part in the study) at any time up to two weeks after taking part and without giving a reason. If you do take part in the study and you change your mind afterwards, you can just contact us and we will destroy all the information you gave us and your data. However, withdrawal after the two-week mark is not possible because the data will have been extracted and analysed.

To do this you will need to create a unique participant code. This is a code made up of six items of any combination, of letters or numbers. Make sure you keep a copy of this code. You will be asked to provide the code during the study so that the researcher can easily recognise and withdraw your data.

What does taking part involve?

In order to take part in the online survey you will need to answer a few demographic questions (i.e. age, gender, occupation). Afterwards you will be asked to fill out questionnaires about your sleep quality and perceived stress, and finally you will be directed to complete a cognitive inhibition task that involves giving answers as quick as possible without compromising accuracy. Completing the survey will take approximately 25 minutes.

What are the benefits of taking part?

By taking part you will be helping to further understanding of how shift work sleep patterns and stress levels could impact the ability to overcome distraction while performing a task.

What are the disadvantages of taking part?

There are no known disadvantages to taking part in this study.

What if there is a problem?

If you have any concerns or complaints about anything to do with this study, please speak to the research team in the first instance and we will do our best to answer your questions. You can email me (Fatima Qatami) or Dr. Roebuck Hettie. Contact details are available at the bottom of this information sheet.

Will the information I give in this study be kept confidential?

Yes, information collected from you for this study will be kept confidential. The data will be stored safely in a password-protected database and accessed only by the mentioned researcher and supervisor. This means that no one outside of the research team will see any of the information you give us. However, anonymised answers from the survey may be used as part of the research findings in the final written report and may be published. Each person taking part in the study will be given a unique participant code to store your data anonymously. In the report you will be identified with a pseudonym. Your name and any identifying details will not be included in the report nor will they be published.

What will happen to the results of the study?

The information you give us will be analysed by the research team and written up into a report; this will form part of the MSc Psychology Research Project and may consequently be published and presented at academic conferences.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed by two members of staff on behalf of the University of Derby [College of Health, Psychology and Social Care Research Ethics Committee](#) and is in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the British Psychological Society; a professional body of psychologists in the UK who overview research to ensure that it protects the safety, rights, wellbeing and dignity of anyone who takes part.

Can I get more information?

If you are interested in taking part in this study but would like some more information before you decide, please talk to me (Fatima Qatami) or you can also contact Dr. Hettie Roebuck.

If I decide to take part what do I do now?

If you do decide to take part in this study, thank you very much. All you need to do is read the consent form thoroughly and complete it.

Contact Details

Fatima Qatami

F.Qatami@unimail.derby.ac.uk

Dr. Hettie Roebuck

H.Roebuck@derby.ac.uk

+44 (0)1332 593876

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

Appendix C

Consent Form

The Effects of Sleep and Stress on Interference Control Among Shift and Non-Shift Workers

Researcher: Fatima Qatami (F.Qatami@unimail.derby.ac.uk)

Supervisor: Dr. Hettie Roebuck (H.Roebuck@derby.ac.uk, +44 (0)1332 593876)

Thank you for your interest in taking part in this research. This research will require you to take part in an online survey.

Anonymous data from the online survey will be used as part of the research findings in the final written report and possibly in publications. All identifying details will remain anonymous, being seen only by the researcher team. There will be no reference to names or any identifying details of the participants in the written report. Your decision to participate is completely voluntary and you may withdraw from this research at any point up to two weeks after participation, you do not need to give a reason or explanation for doing so.

You will be asked to create a unique participant code. This is a code made up of six items of any combination, of letters or numbers. This code must be easy for you to remember as it will enable you to withdraw your research easily if you so chose too. If you have any questions about the research, please feel free to ask the researcher before you decide whether you want to take part.

Statement of Informed Consent

- I understand that I have agreed to participate in the online survey.

- I understand that if; at any time up to two weeks, I decide I no longer wish to take part in this project, I can notify the researcher involved and withdraw immediately.
- I agree that the research project named above has been explained to me to my satisfaction and I have had the opportunity to ask the researcher any questions.
- I understand that anonymous verbatim quotes may be used in the final report and may be published.

GDPR Statement

Researchers will be collecting data from your participation in this study as described in the information sheet and consent form. This is the legal basis on which we are collecting your data and while this allows us to use your data, it also means we have obligations towards you to:

- not seek more information from you than what is essential and necessary for the study.
- make sure that you are not identified by the data by anonymising it using ID codes;
- use your anonymised data only for the purposes of this study and for any relevant publications that arise from it.
- store data safely in password-protected databases to which only the named researchers have access
- not keep your information for longer than is necessary (usually for seven years);
- safely destroy your data by shredding or permanently deleting them

The University of Derby will act as the Data Controller for this study. This means that the University is responsible for looking after your information and using it properly.

Researchers on the project with access to the data are highly qualified and experienced and

have been very careful to ensure the security of your data. The study was approved for its ethical standards by The University of Derby Human Sciences Research Ethics Committee. However, in the unlikely event that you feel you need to make a complaint regarding the use of your information, you can contact the Data Protection Officer at the University of Derby: James Eaglesfield (01332) 591762 or the Information Commissioners Office 0303 123 1113.

Further information about the project can be obtained from Fatima Qatami

(F.Qatami@unimail.derby.ac.uk) or Dr. Hettie Roebuck (email: H.Roebuck@derby.ac.uk /

phone: +44 (0)1332 593876) at the University of Derby, The Enterprise Centre, Bridge Street, Derby DE1 3LD.

I have read and understand the above statements and agree to take part in this study.

- Please tick box to acknowledge the above mentioned statement and give your consent

I confirm I am over 18

- Please tick box

I conform I am free from diagnosed and chronic sleep or psychological disorders (i.e. insomnia, ADHD, ASD)

- Please tick box

Please create a unique ID code made up of the last 3 letters of your surname and the last 3 digits of your phone number. For example, if your name is Jack Miller and your telephone number is 0566938650 then your code will be LER650.

Keep a note of your code as you will need it if you wish to contact the researchers and withdraw your data.

Code: -----

Appendix D
Debrief Form
DEBRIEF FORM

Dear Participant,

Thank you very much for taking part in this research study which explored the area of cognitive control. This study hopes to investigate the effects of sleep and stress on interference control among shift and non-shift workers, which emphasizes the importance of implementing measures that consider shift workers cognitive health, whether these measures are taken by the employer or personally by the shift workers themselves.

- Please tick box to give your informed consent

Your decision to participate is completely voluntary and should you wish to withdraw from the research you may do so at any point, up to two weeks after participation. You will not need to give any reason or explanation for doing so. To withdraw your data simply contact the researcher with your unique participant code (the code made up of numbers or letters) on the details below explaining your wish to withdraw.

Should you have any questions about the research please feel free to contact the researcher on the details below. If your participation in the study has raised any concerns about your emotional or mental health, please contact The Samaritans, a support group, at their 24hr helpline by calling 116123.

Many thanks,

Fatima Qatami (F.Qatami@unimail.derby.ac.uk)

Dr. Hettie Roebuck (H.Roebuck@derby.ac.uk , +44 (0)1332 593876)

Appendix E

Scales

PITTSBURGH SLEEP QUALITY INDEX (PSQI)

Instructions:

The following questions relate to your usual sleep habits during the past month *only*.

Your answers should indicate the most accurate reply for the *majority* of days and nights in the past month. Please answer all questions.

1. During the past month, when have you usually gone to bed at night?

USUAL BED TIME.....

2. During the past month, how long (in minutes) has it usually take you to fall asleep each night?

NUMBER OF MINUTES.....

3. During the past month, when have you usually gotten up in the morning?

USUAL GETTING UP TIME.....

4. During the past month, how many hours of actual sleep did you get at night? (This may be different that the number of hours you spend in bed.)

HOURS OF SLEEP PER NIGHT.....

Instructions:

For each of the remaining questions, check the one best response.

Please answer all questions.

5. During the past month, how often have you had trouble sleeping because you...

a. ... cannot get to sleep within 30 minutes

a. Not during the past month

- b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- b. ... wake up in the middle of the night or early morning
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- c. ... have to get up to use the bathroom
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- d. ... cannot breathe comfortably
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- e. ... cough or snore loudly
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week

- f. ... feel too cold
 - a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- g. ... feel too hot
 - a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- h. ... had bad dreams
 - a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- i. ... have pain
 - a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- j. ... other reason(s), please describe
- k. How often during the past month have you had trouble sleeping because of this?
 - a. Not during the past month

- b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
6. During the past month, how would you rate your sleep quality overall?
- a. Very good
 - b. Fairly good
 - c. Fairly bad
 - d. Very bad
7. During the past month, how often have you taken medicine (prescribed or “over the counter”) to help you sleep?
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
8. During the past month, how often have you had trouble staying awake while driving, eating meals, or engaging in social activity?
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
9. During the past month, how much of a problem has it been for you to keep up enough enthusiasm to get things done?
- a. No problem at all

- b. Only a very slight problem
 - c. Somewhat of a problem
 - d. A very big problem
10. Do you have a bed partner or a roommate?
- a. No bed partner or roommate
 - b. Partner/roommate in other room
 - c. Partner in same room, but not in same bed
 - d. Partner in same bed

If you have a roommate or bed partner, ask him/her how often in the past month you have had...

- a. ... loud snoring
 - a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- b. ... long pauses between breaths while asleep
 - a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- c. ... legs twitching or jerking while you asleep
 - a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week

- d. Three or more times a week
- d. ... episodes of disorientation or confusion during sleep
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week
- e. ... other restlessness while you asleep; please describe
- a. Not during the past month
 - b. Less than once a week
 - c. Once or twice a week
 - d. Three or more times a week

PSS-14

INSTRUCTIONS:

The questions in this scale ask you about your feelings and thoughts during THE LAST MONTH. In each case, you will be asked to indicate your response by ticking the circle representing HOW OFTEN you felt or thought a certain way. Although some of the questions are similar, there are differences between them and you should treat each one as a separate question. The best approach is to answer fairly quickly. That is, don't try to count up the number of times you felt a particular way, but rather indicate the alternative that seems like a reasonable estimate.

	Never	Almost Never	Sometimes	Fairly Often	Very Often
	0	1	2	3	4
1. the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	<input type="radio"/>				
2. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
3. In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and "stressed"?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. In the last month, how often have you dealt successfully with day to day problems and annoyances?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were effectively coping with important changes that were occurring in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	<input type="radio"/>				
9. In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?	<input type="radio"/>				

PSS-14

	Never	Almost Never	Sometimes	Fairly Often	Very Often
	0	1	2	3	4
11. In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that happened that were outside of your control?	<input type="radio"/>				
12. In the last month, how often have you found yourself thinking about things that you have to accomplish?	<input type="radio"/>				
13. In the last month, how often have you been able to control the way you spend your time?	<input type="radio"/>				
14. In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	<input type="radio"/>				

Link to Eriksen Flanker Task

<https://mili2nd.co/n3yb>

Appendix F

Risk assessment

RISK ASSESSEMENT FORM

This form must be completed before any work involving risk to health, safety or welfare is carried out.

Name (of person carrying out task)					Fatima Qatami				
Designation (of person carrying out task) e.g: Student/Year					3 rd year MSc Psychology student				
Task (Description of task being assessed) Survey on the effect of sleep and stress on interference control among shift and non-shift workers.									
Start Date April 1 st , 2021					End Date September 1 st , 2021				
Date (of making the risk assessment)					March 22 nd , 2021				
Location of task					online				
<p>Hazard and Risk: Definitions: A hazard is something with the potential to do harm (to people or property). Risk is the likelihood of the potential for harm being realised. Look only for hazards which you could reasonably expect to result in significant harm under the conditions in the workplace or in the field (i.e. Significant Risk)</p> <p>Consider the activity or work area and identify if any of the hazards listed below are significant. Please highlight those that are relevant</p>									
1	Fall of person	7	Machinery	13	Electricity	19	Substances	25	Drowning
2	Fall of objects	8	Tools/equipment	14	Noise or vibration	20	High pressure	26	Psychological effects
3	Tripping/Slipping	9	Mobile work equipment	15	Hot/cold surfaces	21	Fire/explosion	27	Human error
4	Manual handling	10	Mechanical lifting	16	Workstation layout/space	22	Lighting	26	Violence
5	Repetitive work	11	Display screen equipment	17	Radiation	23	Confined space	29	Peripatetic/lone working
6	Housekeeping/waste material	12	Sharp objects	18	Temperature/weather	24	Buildings and glazing	30	Other(s)
<p>WHO MIGHT BE HARMED? As well as yourself, others may be at risk because of the task that you are undertaking. Think about who may be at risk as a result of your activity. E.g. *other laboratory users, * fellow students, *supervisors, *staff/colleagues, *cleaners, *participants, *members of the public, *contractors, *maintenance personnel, *persons with you in the field</p> <p>Participant</p> <p>Researcher</p>									
<p>LIST HERE ANYONE OR ANY GROUP OF PEOPLE WHO MAY BE AT RISK – State “N/A” if appropriate (If the assessment is for a student project, you may need to write the name of the responsible adult accompanying the student)</p> <p>Participant</p>									

Researcher		
<p>WHAT MEASURES ARE NECESSARY TO CONTROL (REDUCE) THE RISKS? – Only complete this section if it is applicable to your project</p> <p>If there are significant risks the following principles (in order) will help to ensure that the risks are adequately controlled.</p> <p>1 Remove the risk completely i.e., don't do the task, do something less risky. 2 Employ a less risky method of obtaining the same results.</p> <p>3 Prevent Access to the Hazard (e.g. by guarding.) 4 Make sure you are adequately informed of the risks and trained to cope with them.</p> <p>5 Organise work to reduce exposure to the hazard. 6 Be accompanied by an experienced person who can manage the risks.</p> <p>7 Use Personal Protective Equipment. 8 Provide emergency procedures. (Including first aid provision where necessary.)</p>		
Hazards/Risks (What could go wrong)	List here the control measures to be used to reduce the significant risks to a tolerable or trivial level. (How are you going to stop it going wrong?)	Level of risk <i>after</i> control measure High, Medium, Low Refer to University Risk Evaluation Matrix
11. Display screen equipment Level: Tolerable	Participating in the survey requires answering two questionnaires and completing a task using a computer or a laptop. The length of the survey is approximately 25 mins. Participants will be informed about this beforehand. Participants can take breaks throughout most parts of the survey and will be informed of this in the invitation sheet.	Low
26. Psychological effects Level: Tolerable/Moderate	Sleepy quality questionnaire assessed using The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index is unlikely to cause distress to most participants. Participants with sleep disorders have been excluded from the study. Participants have to answer questions regarding how stressed they feel when completing the Perceived Stress Scale, which could distress people who have been diagnosed with certain psychological disorders. Therefore, people with diagnosed psychological disorders have been excluded from the study. The final task requires participants to give correct answers as fast as possible, which may cause discomfort but is very unlikely to cause distress. Participants will be informed of the nature of the questionnaires and tasks they are required to complete in the participant information sheet prior to their participation. Participants will be able to contact the support group The Samaritan by calling their free helpline 116123 in case they have any concerns regarding their mental health. This will be outlined in many stages throughout the survey including the debrief form. Moreover, participants will have to confirm they are over 18 years old to be able to access the survey	Low
29. Peripatetic/lone working Level: Tolerable	The student will reach out to their supervisor in case they feel that working alone is affecting them.	Low
30. other Data breach Level:	Data will be secured in a password-protected file and only on the personal P.C of the researcher. Data will be deleted	Low

Moderate	from online platforms (i.e. Qualtrics) once data collection is complete.	

WHAT STUDENTS NEED TO DO WHEN THE RISK ASSESSMENT FORM IS COMPLETED

It is of paramount importance that the information in the risk assessment is available to you during the process to which it relates. **HAVE A COPY WITH YOU.**

1. Submit as part of the Ethics application
2. Follow the recommendations and control measures made in the assessment.
3. If any of the conditions or procedures change, notify your supervisor immediately. A new assessment must be made.

Appendix G

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-compatible

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Case Processing Summary

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		work	N	Percent	N	Percent	N
RT incompatible - compatible	non shift	99	100.0%	0	0.0%	99	100.0%
	shift	109	100.0%	0	0.0%	109	100.0%
	work						

Descriptives

		work	Statistic	Std.
				Error
RT incompatible - compatible	non shift	Mean	17.5550	2.66849
		95% Confidence	Lower	12.2595
		Interval for Mean	Bound	
		Upper	22.8506	
		Bound		
		5% Trimmed Mean	18.6162	

	Median		17.5817	
	Variance		704.965	
	Std. Deviation		26.55119	
	Minimum		-79.92	
	Maximum		76.74	
	Range		156.66	
	Interquartile Range		28.70	
	Skewness		-.677	.243
	Kurtosis		1.888	.481
shift	Mean		16.8368	2.70926
work	95% Confidence	Lower	11.4665	
	Interval for Mean	Bound		
		Upper	22.2070	
		Bound		
	5% Trimmed Mean		17.9214	
	Median		20.1950	
	Variance		800.068	
	Std. Deviation		28.28547	
	Minimum		-87.86	
	Maximum		77.61	
	Range		165.48	
	Interquartile Range		28.25	

Skewness	-.755	.231
Kurtosis	1.368	.459

Tests of Normality

	work	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
RT incompatible - non shift		.087	99	.061	.964	99	.008
compatible shift		.102	109	.007	.963	109	.004
	work						

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-compatible

Groups: good and bad sleep

Case Processing Summary

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
sleep		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
RT incompatible - compatible	good	88	100.0%	0	0.0%	88	100.0%
	bad	120	100.0%	0	0.0%	120	100.0%

Descriptives

	sleep		Statistic	Std. Error	
RT incompatible - compatible	good	Mean	18.3879	2.56310	
		95% Confidence	Lower	13.2935	
		Interval for Mean	Bound		
			Upper	23.4824	
			Bound		
		5% Trimmed Mean		19.0038	
		Median		19.6498	
		Variance		578.116	
		Std. Deviation		24.04404	
		Minimum		-69.04	
		Maximum		68.59	
		Range		137.62	
		Interquartile Range		26.05	
		Skewness		-.471	.257
		Kurtosis		1.240	.508
			bad	Mean	16.2918
95% Confidence	Lower			10.9225	
Interval for Mean	Bound				
	Upper			21.6612	
	Bound				

5% Trimmed Mean	17.4900	
Median	18.5333	
Variance	882.366	
Std. Deviation	29.70465	
Minimum	-87.86	
Maximum	77.61	
Range	165.48	
Interquartile Range	30.81	
Skewness	-.778	.221
Kurtosis	1.413	.438

Tests of Normality

	sleep	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
RT incompatible -	good	.079	88	.200*	.972	88	.055
compatible	bad	.095	120	.010	.962	120	.002

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-compatible

Groups: low and high

Case Processing Summary

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
stress		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
RT incompatible - compatible	low	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%
	high	101	100.0%	0	0.0%	101	100.0%

Descriptives

				Statistic	Std. Error	
stress						
RT incompatible - compatible	low	Mean		15.2774	2.80120	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	9.7237	
				Upper Bound	20.8310	
		5% Trimmed Mean			16.8630	
		Median			17.5817	
		Variance			839.597	

	Std. Deviation		28.97580	
	Minimum		-87.86	
	Maximum		77.61	
	Range		165.48	
	Interquartile Range		27.62	
	Skewness		-.971	.234
	Kurtosis		2.007	.463
high	Mean		19.1929	2.55100
	95% Confidence	Lower	14.1317	
	Interval for Mean	Bound		
		Upper	24.2540	
		Bound		
	5% Trimmed Mean		19.6803	
	Median		20.2403	
	Variance		657.269	
	Std. Deviation		25.63725	
	Minimum		-57.81	
	Maximum		76.74	
	Range		134.54	
	Interquartile Range		30.37	
	Skewness		-.285	.240
	Kurtosis		.400	.476

Tests of Normality

	stress	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
RT incompatible -	low	.113	107	.002	.943	107	.000
compatible	high	.058	101	.200*	.989	101	.574

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-neutral

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Case Processing Summary

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
Work		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
RT incompatible-neutral	non-shift	99	100.0%	0	0.0%	99	100.0%
	work						
	shift work	109	100.0%	0	0.0%	109	100.0%

Descriptives

	Work		Statistic	Std. Error	
RT incompatible- neutral	non-shift	Mean	61.0593	4.57527	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	51.9798	
	work		Upper Bound	70.1387	
		5% Trimmed Mean		58.5718	
		Median		52.9709	
	Variance		2072.373		
	Std. Deviation		45.52332		
	Minimum		-21.29		
	Maximum		258.77		
	Range		280.06		
	Interquartile Range		59.11		
	Skewness		1.035	.243	
	Kurtosis		2.757	.481	
	shift work	Mean		52.5639	4.77725
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	43.0945	
		Upper Bound	62.0332		

5% Trimmed Mean	55.0078	
Median	55.3684	
Variance	2487.606	
Std. Deviation	49.87590	
Minimum	-170.51	
Maximum	168.78	
Range	339.29	
Interquartile Range	58.49	
Skewness	-1.217	.231
Kurtosis	4.578	.459

Tests of Normality

	Work	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
RT incompatible- neutral	non-shift	.086	99	.066	.942	99	.000
	work						
	shift work	.079	109	.090	.923	109	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-neutral

Groups: good and bad sleep

Case Processing Summary

	Sleep	Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
RT incompatible-	good	88	100.0%	0	0.0%	88	100.0%
neutral	bad	120	100.0%	0	0.0%	120	100.0%

Descriptives

	Sleep	Statistic	Std.
			Error
RT incompatible-	good	Mean	51.4349
neutral		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	42.3675
		Lower Bound	
		Upper Bound	60.5023
		5% Trimmed Mean	49.6337
		Median	45.8833
		Variance	1831.404
		Std. Deviation	42.79491

	Minimum		-64.46	
	Maximum		258.77	
	Range		323.23	
	Interquartile Range		52.38	
	Skewness		1.192	.257
	Kurtosis		5.354	.508
bad	Mean		60.4005	4.67490
	95% Confidence	Lower	51.1437	
	Interval for Mean	Bound		
		Upper	69.6573	
		Bound		
	5% Trimmed Mean		62.1097	
	Median		59.3675	
	Variance		2622.564	
	Std. Deviation		51.21098	
	Minimum		-170.51	
	Maximum		189.40	
	Range		359.91	
	Interquartile Range		60.35	
	Skewness		-1.030	.221
	Kurtosis		4.235	.438

Tests of Normality

	Sleep	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
RT incompatible-	good	.073	88	.200*	.923	88	.000
neutral	bad	.065	120	.200*	.935	120	.000

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-neutral

Groups: low and high stress

Case Processing Summary

Stress	Valid	Cases	
		Missing	Total

		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
RT incompatible- neutral	low	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%
	high	101	100.0%	0	0.0%	101	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
RT incompatible- neutral	low	Mean	49.4108	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean		
		Lower Bound	40.5007	
		Upper Bound	58.3209	
		5% Trimmed Mean	50.6007	
		Median	49.1303	
		Variance	2161.133	
		Std. Deviation	46.48798	
		Minimum	-170.51	
		Maximum	148.89	
		Range	319.40	
		Interquartile Range	63.59	
		Skewness	-.895	.234

	Kurtosis		3.632	.463
high	Mean		64.2314	4.82368
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	54.6614	
		Upper Bound	73.8015	
	5% Trimmed Mean		63.1606	
	Median		56.4878	
	Variance		2350.058	
	Std. Deviation		48.47740	
	Minimum		-141.95	
	Maximum		258.77	
	Range		400.72	
	Interquartile Range		51.02	
	Skewness		.156	.240
	Kurtosis		4.633	.476

Tests of Normality

Stress	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
low	.076	107	.149	.946	107	.000

RT incompatible- neutral	high	.088	101	.050	.932	101	.000
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a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-compatible

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Case Processing Summary

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
Work		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
BIS incompatible-compatible	non-shift work	99	100.0%	0	0.0%	99	100.0%
	shift work	109	100.0%	0	0.0%	109	100.0%

Descriptives

		Work	Statistic	Std. Error
BIS incompatible-compatible	non-shift work	Mean	-.7785	.08558
	work	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.9483
		Upper Bound	-.6087	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.7017	
	Median	-.6441		

	Variance		.725	
	Std. Deviation		.85153	
	Minimum		-4.20	
	Maximum		.72	
	Range		4.92	
	Interquartile Range		.82	
	Skewness		-1.589	.243
	Kurtosis		4.002	.481
shift work	Mean		-.7295	.07717
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.8824	
		Upper Bound	-.5765	
	5% Trimmed Mean		-.6937	
	Median		-.7003	
	Variance		.649	
	Std. Deviation		.80566	
	Minimum		-5.18	
	Maximum		1.14	
	Range		6.32	
	Interquartile Range		.98	
	Skewness		-1.524	.231
	Kurtosis		7.816	.459

Tests of Normality

		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
Work		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-compatible	non-shift	.138	99	.000	.881	99	.000
	work						
	shift work	.096	109	.015	.905	109	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-compatible

Groups: good and bad sleep

Case Processing Summary

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		Sleep	N	Percent	N	Percent	N
BIS incompatible- compatible	good	88	100.0%	0	0.0%	88	100.0%
	bad	120	100.0%	0	0.0%	120	100.0%

Descriptives

		Sleep		Statistic	Std. Error		
BIS incompatible- compatible	good	Mean		-.7009	.07520		
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	-.8504		
				Upper Bound	-.5514		
		5% Trimmed Mean			-.6523		
		Median			-.6053		
		Variance			.498		
		Std. Deviation			.70543		
		Minimum			-3.73		
		Maximum			.75		
		Range			4.48		
		Interquartile Range			.85		
		Skewness			-1.390	.257	
		Kurtosis			4.215	.508	
		bad	Mean		-.7909	.08266	
			95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	-.9546	
					Upper Bound		

	Upper Bound	-.6272	
	5% Trimmed Mean	-.7294	
	Median	-.7279	
	Variance	.820	
	Std. Deviation	.90555	
	Minimum	-5.18	
	Maximum	1.14	
	Range	6.32	
	Interquartile Range	.90	
	Skewness	-1.535	.221
	Kurtosis	5.532	.438

Tests of Normality

	Sleep	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-	good	.079	88	.200*	.911	88	.000
compatible	bad	.111	120	.001	.900	120	.000

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

 Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-compatible

Groups: low and high stress

Case Processing Summary

	Stress	Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
BIS incompatible-compatible	low	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%
	high	101	100.0%	0	0.0%	101	100.0%

Descriptives

	Stress		Statistic	Std.
				Error
BIS incompatible-compatible	low	Mean	-.7243	.08144
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.8858
		Upper Bound	-.5628	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.6639	

	Median		-.6006	
	Variance		.710	
	Std. Deviation		.84241	
	Minimum		-4.20	
	Maximum		.82	
	Range		5.02	
	Interquartile Range		.95	
	Skewness		-1.327	.234
	Kurtosis		3.435	.463
high	Mean		-.7830	.08077
	95% Confidence	Lower	-.9433	
	Interval for Mean	Bound		
		Upper	-.6228	
		Bound		
	5% Trimmed Mean		-.7294	
	Median		-.7703	
	Variance		.659	
	Std. Deviation		.81169	
	Minimum		-5.18	
	Maximum		1.14	
	Range		6.32	
	Interquartile Range		.83	

Skewness	-1.854	.240
Kurtosis	8.734	.476

Tests of Normality

	Stress	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-	low	.094	107	.022	.918	107	.000
compatible	high	.116	101	.002	.871	101	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-neutral

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Case Processing Summary

Work	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent

BIS incompatible-neutral	non-shift	99	100.0%	0	0.0%	99	100.0%
	work						
	shift work	109	100.0%	0	0.0%	109	100.0%

Descriptives

	Work		Statistic	Std. Error	
BIS incompatible-neutral	non-shift	Mean	1.2958	.10748	
	work	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.0825	
			Upper Bound	1.5091	
		5% Trimmed Mean		1.2081	
		Median	1.0377		
		Variance	1.144		
		Std. Deviation	1.06937		
		Minimum	-.69		
		Maximum	6.71		
		Range	7.41		
		Interquartile Range	1.08		
		Skewness	1.937	.243	
		Kurtosis	6.897	.481	
	shift work	Mean	1.2714	.09667	

95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.0798	
	Upper Bound	1.4630	
5% Trimmed Mean		1.2135	
Median		1.1778	
Variance		1.019	
Std. Deviation		1.00922	
Minimum		-.65	
Maximum		7.08	
Range		7.72	
Interquartile Range		1.15	
Skewness		1.832	.231
Kurtosis		9.082	.459

Tests of Normality

	Work	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-neutral	non-shift	.139	99	.000	.867	99	.000
	work						
	shift work	.080	109	.081	.890	109	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-neutral

Groups: good and bad sleep

Case Processing Summary

	Sleep	Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
BIS incompatible-neutral	good	88	100.0%	0	0.0%	88	100.0%
	bad	120	100.0%	0	0.0%	120	100.0%

Descriptives

	Sleep	Statistic	Std.
			Error
BIS incompatible-neutral	good	Mean	1.0863
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	.8943
		Lower Bound	
		Upper Bound	1.2783

	5% Trimmed Mean		1.0319	
	Median		.9514	
	Variance		.821	
	Std. Deviation		.90623	
	Minimum		-.69	
	Maximum		4.99	
	Range		5.68	
	Interquartile Range		1.11	
	Skewness		1.222	.257
	Kurtosis		3.157	.508
bad	Mean		1.4273	.10068
	95% Confidence	Lower	1.2279	
	Interval for Mean	Bound		
		Upper	1.6266	
		Bound		
	5% Trimmed Mean		1.3473	
	Median		1.2911	
	Variance		1.216	
	Std. Deviation		1.10290	
	Minimum		-.65	
	Maximum		7.08	
	Range		7.72	

Interquartile Range	1.13	
Skewness	2.102	.221
Kurtosis	8.804	.438

Tests of Normality

	Sleep	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-	good	.104	88	.021	.932	88	.000
neutral	bad	.110	120	.001	.852	120	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptive statistics and normality tests

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-neutral

Groups: low and high stress

Case Processing Summary

Stress	Valid	Cases	
		Missing	Total

		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
BIS incompatible-neutral	low	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%
	high	101	100.0%	0	0.0%	101	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error		
BIS incompatible-neutral	low	Mean	1.2726	.10507	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.0643	
			Upper Bound	1.4809	
		5% Trimmed Mean	1.1948		
		Median	1.1778		
		Variance	1.181		
		Std. Deviation	1.08682		
		Minimum	-.69		
		Maximum	6.71		
		Range	7.41		
		Interquartile Range	1.32		
		Skewness	1.616	.234	

	Kurtosis		5.754	.463
high	Mean		1.2941	.09793
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.0998	
		Upper Bound	1.4884	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1.2262	
	Median		1.1134	
	Variance		.969	
	Std. Deviation		.98423	
	Minimum		-.65	
	Maximum		7.08	
	Range		7.72	
	Interquartile Range		1.04	
	Skewness		2.273	.240
	Kurtosis		11.171	.476

Tests of Normality

Stress	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
low	.079	107	.097	.902	107	.000

BIS incompatible- neutral	high	.122	101	.001	.851	101	.000
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a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Appendix H

Mann-Whitney U Tests and correlations

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-compatible

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Ranks

	work	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
RT incompatible - compatible	non shift	99	103.66	10262.50
	shift	109	105.26	11473.50
	work			
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

RT

incompatible

- compatible

Mann-Whitney U	5312.500
Wilcoxon W	10262.500
Z	-.191
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.848

a. Grouping Variable: work

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-compatible

Groups: good and bad sleep groups

Ranks

	sleep	N	Mean	Sum of
			Rank	Ranks
RT incompatible - compatible	good	88	105.12	9250.50
	bad	120	104.05	12485.50
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

RT

incompatible

- compatible

Mann-Whitney U	5225.500
Wilcoxon W	12485.500
Z	-.127
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.899

a. Grouping Variable: sleep

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-compatible

Groups: high and low stress

Ranks

	stress	N	Mean	Sum of
			Rank	Ranks
RT incompatible - compatible	low	107	101.37	10847.00
	high	101	107.81	10889.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

RT

incompatible

- compatible

Mann-Whitney U	5069.000
Wilcoxon W	10847.000
Z	-.771

Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.441
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a. Grouping Variable: stress

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-neutral

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Ranks

	work	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
RT incompatible - neutral	non shift	99	106.92	10585.00
	shift	109	102.30	11151.00
	work			
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

RT

incompatible

- neutral

Mann-Whitney U	5156.000
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Wilcoxon W	11151.000
Z	-.552
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.581

a. Grouping Variable: work

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-neutral

Groups: good and bad sleep

Ranks

	sleep		Mean	Sum of
	good	N	Rank	Ranks
RT incompatible -	good	88	94.14	8284.50
neutral	bad	120	112.10	13451.50
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

RT

incompatible

- neutral

Mann-Whitney U	4368.500
Wilcoxon W	8284.500
Z	-2.125
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.034

a. Grouping Variable: sleep

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: RT incompatible-neutral

Groups: low and high stress

Ranks

	stress	N	Mean	Sum of
			Rank	Ranks
RT incompatible - neutral	low	107	96.23	10296.50
	high	101	113.26	11439.50
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

RT
incompatible
- neutral

Mann-Whitney U	4518.500
Wilcoxon W	10296.500
Z	-2.040
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.041

a. Grouping Variable: stress

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-compatible

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Ranks

	work	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
BIS incompatible - compatible	non shift	99	105.11	10406.00
	shift	109	103.94	11330.00
	work			
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

BIS

incompatible

- compatible

Mann-Whitney U	5335.000
Wilcoxon W	11330.000
Z	-.140
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.889

a. Grouping Variable: work

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-compatible

Groups: good and bad sleep

Ranks

	sleep	N	Mean	Sum of
			Rank	Ranks
BIS incompatible - compatible	good	88	108.20	9522.00
	bad	120	101.78	12214.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

BIS

incompatible

- compatible

Mann-Whitney U	4954.000
Wilcoxon W	12214.000
Z	-.760
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.447

a. Grouping Variable: sleep

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-compatible

Groups: low and high stress

Ranks

	stress	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
BIS incompatible - compatible	low	107	108.31	11589.00
	high	101	100.47	10147.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

BIS

incompatible

- compatible

Mann-Whitney U	4996.000
Wilcoxon W	10147.000
Z	-.939
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.348

a. Grouping Variable: stress

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-neutral

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Ranks

	work	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
	non shift	99	103.22	10219.00

BIS incompatible -	shift	109	105.66	11517.00
neutral	work			
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

BIS

incompatible

- neutral

Mann-Whitney U	5269.000
Wilcoxon W	10219.000
Z	-.292
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.770

a. Grouping Variable: work

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-neutral

Groups: good and bad sleep

Ranks

	sleep	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
BIS incompatible - neutral	good	88	91.64	8064.00
	bad	120	113.93	13672.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

BIS

incompatible

- neutral

Mann-Whitney U	4148.000
Wilcoxon W	8064.000
Z	-2.640
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.008

a. Grouping Variable: sleep

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: BIS incompatible-neutral

Groups: low and high stress

Ranks

	stress	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
BIS incompatible - neutral	low	107	103.43	11067.00
	high	101	105.63	10669.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

BIS incompatible - neutral

Mann-Whitney U	5289.000
Wilcoxon W	11067.000
Z	-.264
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.792

a. Grouping Variable: stress

Correlations

			PS	PS	Ag	Experi	RT	RT	BIS	BIS
			QI	S	e	ence	incompat	incompat	incompat	BIS
							ible-	ible-	ible-	incompat
							compatib	neutral	compatib	ible-
							le	le	le	neutral
Spearman's rho	PSQI	Correlation Coefficient	1.00	.535**	-.050	-.148*	-.032	.108	-.034	.125
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.473	.042	.644	.121	.627	.071
		N	208	208	208	189	208	208	208	208
	PSS	Correlation Coefficient	.535**	1.00	-.188**	-.129	-.007	.126	-.044	.010

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.078	.922	.070	.532	.884
	N	208	208	208	189	208	208	208	208
Age	Correlation Coefficient	-.050	-.188**	1.000	.622**	.090	-.094	-.117	.078
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.473	.006	.000	.000	.195	.178	.092	.266
	N	208	208	208	189	208	208	208	208
Experience	Correlation Coefficient	-.148*	-.129	.622**	1.000	.159*	-.005	.000	-.037
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.042	.078	.000	.000	.029	.942	.997	.613
	N	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189
RT incompatible-compatibile	Correlation Coefficient	-.032	-.007	.090	.159*	1.000	.441**	-.453**	.274**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.644	.922	.195	.029	.000	.000	.000	.000

	N	208	208	208	189	208	208	208	208
RT	Correla	.10	.12	-	-.005	.441**	1.000	-.213**	.603**
incompat	tion	8	6	.09					
ible-	Coeffic			4					
neutral	ient								
	Sig. (2-	.12	.07	.17	.942	.000	.	.002	.000
	tailed)	1	0	8					
	N	208	208	208	189	208	208	208	208
BIS	Correla	-	-	-	.000	-.453**	-.213**	1.000	-.578**
incompat	tion	.03	.04	.11					
ible-	Coeffic	4	4	7					
compatib	ient								
le	Sig. (2-	.62	.53	.09	.997	.000	.002	.	.000
	tailed)	7	2	2					
	N	208	208	208	189	208	208	208	208
BIS	Correla	.12	.01	.07	-.037	.274**	.603**	-.578**	1.000
incompat	tion	5	0	8					
ible-	Coeffic								
neutral	ient								
	Sig. (2-	.07	.88	.26	.613	.000	.000	.000	.
	tailed)	1	4	6					
	N	208	208	208	189	208	208	208	208

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

BIS	Correlat	-	.064	-	.016	-.196*	-	.590**	1.000	-.029
incomp- neutral	ion Coeffici ent	.131		.097			.609**			
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.174	.508	.316	.872	.041	.000	.000	.	.767
	N	109	109	109	109	109	109	109	109	107
educati on	Correlat ion Coeffici ent	.348 **	.190*	.045	.032	.118	.051	-.022	-.029	1.000
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.049	.644	.743	.226	.604	.824	.767	.
	N	107	107	107	107	107	107	107	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: PSQI score

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Ranks

	Work	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
PSQI	non-shift work	99	90.24	8934.00
	shift work	109	117.45	12802.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

	PSQI
Mann-Whitney U	3984.000
Wilcoxon W	8934.000
Z	-3.271
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.001

a. Grouping Variable: Work

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variable: PSS score

Groups: chronotypes

Ranks

	Type of person	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
PSS	early bird	50	69.05	3452.50
	night owl	109	85.02	9267.50
	Total	159		

Test Statistics^a

PSS

Mann-Whitney U	2177.500
Wilcoxon W	3452.500
Z	-2.033
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.042

a. Grouping Variable: Type of person

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variables: RTs and PEs of compatible, incompatible,
and neutral trials

Groups: shift and non-shift work

Ranks

	Work	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
PEcom	non-shift work	99	109.00	10791.00
	shift work	109	100.41	10945.00
	Total	208		
PEincom	non-shift work	99	107.70	10662.50
	shift work	109	101.59	11073.50
	Total	208		
PEneu	non-shift work	99	113.34	11221.00
	shift work	109	96.47	10515.00
	Total	208		
RTcom	non-shift work	99	99.90	9890.00

	shift work	109	108.68	11846.00
	Total	208		
RTincom	non-shift	99	100.33	9933.00
	work			
	shift work	109	108.28	11803.00
	Total	208		
RTneu	non-shift	99	97.73	9675.00
	work			
	shift work	109	110.65	12061.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

	PEcom	PEincom	PEneu	RTcom	RTincom	RTneu
Mann-Whitney U	4950.000	5078.500	4520.000	4940.000	4983.000	4725.000
Wilcoxon W	10945.000	11073.500	10515.000	9890.000	9933.000	9675.000
Z	-1.030	-.732	-2.025	-1.051	-.952	-1.547
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.303	.464	.043	.293	.341	.122

a. Grouping Variable: Work

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variables: RTs and PEs of compatible, incompatible, and neutral trials

Groups: good and bad sleep

Ranks

	Sleep	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
PEcom	good	88	92.14	8108.50
	bad	120	113.56	13627.50
	Total	208		
PEincom	good	88	91.85	8083.00
	bad	120	113.78	13653.00
	Total	208		
PEneu	good	88	97.74	8601.50
	bad	120	109.45	13134.50
	Total	208		
RTcom	good	88	98.02	8626.00
	bad	120	109.25	13110.00
	Total	208		
RTincom	good	88	99.20	8730.00
	bad	120	108.38	13006.00
	Total	208		

RTneu	good	88	106.05	9332.00
	bad	120	103.37	12404.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

	PEcom	PEincom	PEneu	RTcom	RTincom	RTneu
Mann-Whitney U	4192.500	4167.000	4685.500	4710.000	4814.000	5144.000
Wilcoxon W	8108.500	8083.000	8601.500	8626.000	8730.000	12404.000
Z	-2.542	-2.599	-1.390	-1.329	-1.087	-.317
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	.009	.164	.184	.277	.751

a. Grouping Variable: Sleep

Mann-Whitney Test

Dependent variables: RTs and PEs of compatible,

incompatible, and neutral trials

Groups: low and high stress

Ranks

	Stress	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
PEcom	low	107	102.67	10986.00
	high	101	106.44	10750.00
	Total	208		
PEincom	low	107	97.95	10480.50
	high	101	111.44	11255.50
	Total	208		
PEneu	low	107	95.05	10170.00
	high	101	114.51	11566.00
	Total	208		
RTcom	low	107	104.66	11199.00
	high	101	104.33	10537.00
	Total	208		
RTincom	low	107	104.42	11173.00
	high	101	104.58	10563.00
	Total	208		
RTneu	low	107	110.70	11845.00
	high	101	97.93	9891.00
	Total	208		

Test Statistics^a

	PEcom	PEincom	PEneu	RTcom	RTincom	RTneu
Mann-Whitney U	5208.000	4702.500	4392.000	5386.000	5395.000	4740.000
Wilcoxon W	10986.000	10480.500	10170.000	10537.000	11173.000	9891.000
Z	-.452	-1.618	-2.338	-.040	-.020	-1.529
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.651	.106	.019	.968	.984	.126

a. Grouping Variable: Stress

Appendix I**Normality tests of Log(10) transformed data**

Outliers were checked using the the 3 SD method. Data was winsorized to achieve normality, however failed. Also, the results remained the same before and after winsorizing.

Descriptives

		Sleep	Statistic	Std. Error	
BIS incompatible-compatible (log10)	bad	Mean	-.4565	.07507	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.6052	
			Upper Bound	-.3079	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3438		
		Median	-.2789		
		Variance	.676		
		Std. Deviation	.82238		
		Minimum	-4.03		
		Maximum	.60		
		Range	4.64		
		Interquartile Range	.60		
		Skewness	-2.930	.221	
		Kurtosis	10.259	.438	
	good	Mean	-.3044	.06085	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.4254	
			Upper Bound	-.1835	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.2386		
		Median	-.2280		
		Variance	.326		
		Std. Deviation	.57083		
		Minimum	-4.03		
		Maximum	.42		
		Range	4.45		
Interquartile Range	.41				
Skewness	-3.822	.257			
Kurtosis	21.758	.508			
BIS incompatible-neutral (log10)	bad	Mean	-.4829	.08772	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.6566	
			Upper Bound	-.3092	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3735		
		Median	-.2974		
		Variance	.923		
		Std. Deviation	.96091		
		Minimum	-4.35		
		Maximum	2.28		
		Range	6.63		
		Interquartile Range	.63		
		Skewness	-2.280	.221	
		Kurtosis	7.789	.438	
	good	Mean	-.2795	.06506	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.4088	
			Upper Bound	-.1502	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.2142		
		Median	-.1508		
		Variance	.373		
		Std. Deviation	.61036		
		Minimum	-4.35		
		Maximum	.65		
		Range	5.00		
Interquartile Range	.52				
Skewness	-3.829	.257			
Kurtosis	22.633	.508			

Tests of Normality

	Sleep	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-compatible (log10)	bad	.226	120	.000	.686	120	.000
	good	.206	88	.000	.682	88	.000
BIS incompatible-neutral (log10)	bad	.214	120	.000	.736	120	.000
	good	.178	88	.000	.691	88	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptives

	Stress		Statistic	Std. Error	
BIS incompatible– compatible (log10)	high	Mean	-.3673	.05644	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.4793	
			Upper Bound	-.2554	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3061		
		Median	-.2995		
		Variance	.322		
		Std. Deviation	.56721		
		Minimum	-4.03		
		Maximum	.60		
		Range	4.64		
		Interquartile Range	.40		
		Skewness	-3.363	.240	
		Kurtosis	18.318	.476	
		low	Mean	-.4156	.08277
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	-.5797	
			Upper Bound	-.2515	
	5% Trimmed Mean		-.2884		
	Median		-.2165		
	Variance		.733		
	Std. Deviation		.85622		
	Minimum		-4.03		
	Maximum		.52		
Range	4.56				
Interquartile Range	.52				
Skewness	-3.001	.234			
Kurtosis	10.181	.463			
BIS incompatible–neutral (log10)	high	Mean	-.3094	.07144	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.4512	
			Upper Bound	-.1677	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.2582		
		Median	-.1520		
		Variance	.516		
		Std. Deviation	.71799		
		Minimum	-4.35		
		Maximum	2.28		
		Range	6.63		
		Interquartile Range	.60		
		Skewness	-2.049	.240	
		Kurtosis	12.193	.476	
		low	Mean	-.4793	.08974
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	-.6573	
			Upper Bound	-.3014	
	5% Trimmed Mean		-.3438		
	Median		-.2370		
	Variance		.862		
	Std. Deviation		.92827		
	Minimum		-4.35		
	Maximum		.67		
Range	5.02				
Interquartile Range	.54				
Skewness	-2.935	.234			
Kurtosis	9.678	.463			

Tests of Normality

	Stress	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-compatible (log10)	high	.169	101	.000	.731	101	.000
	low	.233	107	.000	.658	107	.000
BIS incompatible-neutral (log10)	high	.156	101	.000	.776	101	.000
	low	.240	107	.000	.661	107	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptives^{a,b}

	Work		Statistic	Std. Error	
BIS incompatible-compatible (log10)	1	Mean	-.3658	.06895	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.5024	
			Upper Bound	-.2291	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.2716		
		Median	-.2297		
		Variance	.518		
		Std. Deviation	.71985		
		Minimum	-4.03		
		Maximum	.60		
		Range	4.64		
	Interquartile Range	.47			
	Skewness	-3.714	.231		
	Kurtosis	16.995	.459		
	2	Mean	-.4248	.07520	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.5741	
			Upper Bound	-.2756	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3317		
		Median	-.2887		
		Variance	.554		
		Std. Deviation	.74444		
Minimum		-4.03			
Maximum		.52			
Range		4.56			
Interquartile Range	.59				
Skewness	-2.845	.244			
Kurtosis	10.663	.483			
BIS incompatible-neutral (log10)	1	Mean	-.4307	.07929	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.5878	
			Upper Bound	-.2735	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3203		
		Median	-.2333		
		Variance	.685		
		Std. Deviation	.82777		
		Minimum	-4.35		
		Maximum	.93		
		Range	5.28		
	Interquartile Range	.53			
	Skewness	-3.176	.231		
	Kurtosis	12.561	.459		
	2	Mean	-.3625	.08584	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.5329	
			Upper Bound	-.1922	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.2756		
		Median	-.2165		
		Variance	.722		
		Std. Deviation	.84975		
Minimum		-4.35			
Maximum		2.28			
Range		6.63			
Interquartile Range	.60				
Skewness	-2.339	.244			
Kurtosis	10.240	.483			

a. BIS incompatible-compatible (log10) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

b. BIS incompatible-neutral (log10) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

Tests of Normality^{a,c}

	Work	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^b			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-compatible (log10)	1	.218	109	.000	.623	109	.000
	2	.198	98	.000	.724	98	.000
BIS incompatible-neutral (log10)	1	.211	109	.000	.671	109	.000
	2	.194	98	.000	.739	98	.000

a. BIS incompatible-compatible (log10) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

b. Lilliefors Significance Correction

c. BIS incompatible-neutral (log10) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

Normality tests of SQRT transformed data

Descriptives

		Sleep	Statistic	Std. Error	
BIS incompatible– compatible (SQRT)	bad	Mean	-.4940	.07245	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.6375	
			Upper Bound	-.3506	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.4021		
		Median	-.3234		
		Variance	.630		
		Std. Deviation	.79363		
		Minimum	-3.63		
		Maximum	.66		
		Range	4.29		
	Interquartile Range	.72			
	Skewness	-2.241	.221		
	Kurtosis	6.626	.438		
	good	Mean	-.3545	.06304	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.4798	
			Upper Bound	-.2292	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.2929		
		Median	-.2866		
		Variance	.350		
		Std. Deviation	.59139		
Minimum		-3.63			
Maximum		.47			
Range		4.10			
Interquartile Range	.50				
Skewness	-2.675	.257			
Kurtosis	11.846	.508			
BIS incompatible–neutral (SQRT)	bad	Mean	.7684	.05963	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	.6503	
			Upper Bound	.8865	
		5% Trimmed Mean	.7899		
		Median	.7285		
		Variance	.427		
		Std. Deviation	.65325		
		Minimum	-1.48		
		Maximum	2.58		
		Range	4.06		
	Interquartile Range	.81			
	Skewness	-.566	.221		
	Kurtosis	1.717	.438		
	good	Mean	.6803	.06026	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	.5606	
			Upper Bound	.8001	
		5% Trimmed Mean	.6491		
		Median	.6135		
		Variance	.320		
		Std. Deviation	.56528		
Minimum		-.79			
Maximum		2.91			
Range		3.70			
Interquartile Range	.67				
Skewness	1.039	.257			
Kurtosis	3.237	.508			

Tests of Normality

	Sleep	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-compatible (SQRT)	bad	.177	120	.000	.786	120	.000
	good	.176	88	.000	.786	88	.000
BIS incompatible-neutral (SQRT)	bad	.052	120	.200*	.968	120	.006
	good	.074	88	.200*	.933	88	.000

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptives

	Stress		Statistic	Std. Error	
BIS incompatible–compatible (SQRT)	high	Mean	-.4259	.05889	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.5428	
			Upper Bound	-.3091	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3691		
		Median	-.3792		
		Variance	.350		
		Std. Deviation	.59187		
		Minimum	-3.63		
		Maximum	.66		
		Range	4.29		
		Interquartile Range	.52		
	Skewness	-2.306	.240		
	Kurtosis	9.624	.476		
	low	Mean	-.4435	.07930	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.6008	
			Upper Bound	-.2863	
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3391		
		Median	-.2792		
		Variance	.673		
		Std. Deviation	.82027		
		Minimum	-3.63		
		Maximum	.66		
Range		4.29			
Interquartile Range		.66			
Skewness	-2.374	.234			
Kurtosis	6.895	.463			
BIS incompatible–neutral (SQRT)	high	Mean	.8475	.06246	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	.7236	
			Upper Bound	.9715	
		5% Trimmed Mean	.8263		
		Median	.7411		
		Variance	.394		
		Std. Deviation	.62774		
		Minimum	-1.48		
		Maximum	2.91		
		Range	4.38		
		Interquartile Range	.74		
	Skewness	.356	.240		
	Kurtosis	2.485	.476		
	low	Mean	.6213	.05705	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	.5082	
			Upper Bound	.7344	
		5% Trimmed Mean	.6401		
		Median	.6286		
		Variance	.348		
		Std. Deviation	.59008		
		Minimum	-1.48		
		Maximum	1.80		
Range		3.28			
Interquartile Range		.85			
Skewness	-.530	.234			
Kurtosis	1.010	.463			

Tests of Normality

	Stress	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-compatible (SQRT)	high	.147	101	.000	.825	101	.000
	low	.174	107	.000	.760	107	.000
BIS incompatible-neutral (SQRT)	high	.082	101	.093	.952	101	.001
	low	.068	107	.200*	.972	107	.022

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Descriptives^{a,b}

	Work		Statistic	Std. Error		
BIS incompatible-compatible (SQRT)	1	Mean	-.4067	.06647		
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.5385		
			Upper Bound	-.2750		
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3271			
		Median	-.2877			
		Variance	.482			
		Std. Deviation	.69393			
		Minimum	-3.63			
		Maximum	.66			
		Range	4.29			
		Interquartile Range	.58			
		Skewness	-2.811	.231		
		Kurtosis	11.164	.459		
	2	Mean	-.4699	.07540		
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	-.6195		
			Upper Bound	-.3203		
		5% Trimmed Mean	-.3891			
		Median	-.3398			
		Variance	.557			
		Std. Deviation	.74639			
Minimum		-3.63				
Maximum		.66				
Range		4.29				
Interquartile Range		.69				
Skewness		-2.107	.244			
Kurtosis		6.236	.483			
BIS incompatible-neutral (SQRT)		1	Mean	.6787	.05767	
			95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	.5644	
				Upper Bound	.7930	
			5% Trimmed Mean	.7008		
	Median		.6742			
	Variance		.362			
	Std. Deviation		.60206			
	Minimum		-1.48			
	Maximum		2.08			
	Range		3.56			
	Interquartile Range		.74			
	Skewness		-.652	.231		
	Kurtosis		1.917	.459		
	2	Mean	.7888	.06421		
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	.6614		
			Upper Bound	.9163		
		5% Trimmed Mean	.7616			
		Median	.6977			
		Variance	.404			
		Std. Deviation	.63568			
Minimum		-1.15				
Maximum		2.91				
Range		4.06				
Interquartile Range		.75				
Skewness		.548	.244			
Kurtosis		1.701	.483			

a. BIS incompatible-compatible (SQRT) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

b. BIS incompatible-neutral (SQRT) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

Tests of Normality^{a,c}

	Work	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^b			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
BIS incompatible-compatible (SQRT)	1	.169	109	.000	.742	109	.000
	2	.164	98	.000	.816	98	.000
BIS incompatible-neutral (SQRT)	1	.063	109	.200 [*]	.962	109	.003
	2	.065	98	.200 [*]	.961	98	.005

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. BIS incompatible-compatible (SQRT) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

b. Lilliefors Significance Correction

c. BIS incompatible-neutral (SQRT) is constant when Work = . It has been omitted.

